

**SCHOLARSHIP AS A STUDENT SUPPORT SERVICE: AWARENESS
AND ATTITUDINAL PERSPECTIVE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN
TEACHERS TRAINING INSTITUTES**

(A Research Report Submitted under RUSA 2.0 component 8 grant)

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PREFACE

The work embodied in this research project report entitled, “Scholarship as a part of Student Service: Awareness & Attitudinal Perspective of Stakeholders in Teachers Training Institute” has been carried out in Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, West Bengal funded by RUSA 2.0 component 8 grant. It represents a conclusion of effort and learning that has been taken place over a period of six months (Oct. 2022 to March, 2023).

The report gives a general idea of the nature of awareness and attitude of BEd students towards scholarship schemes available for them in West Bengal. Similarly, the picture of awareness as well as attitude of the Nodal persons/Officers at institute level about those scholarship schemes also studied. This report comprises of five chapters.

The first Chapter tries to make an elaborate analysis of the concepts of Attitude, awareness, several scholarship schemes and their interrelationship. It also describes the purpose with limitation of the study. The second Chapter is assigned to the researches already done in this field and its related areas, so as to find out the gaps in research and arrive at the problem to be investigated. Here the relationships among the various studies are analyzed and how they related with several context are presented in graphical way. The third Chapter tries to explain the methodological aspects. In fourth Chapter quantitative and qualitative analyses of the data are done, the results are presented and interpreted accordingly. Finally, in fifth Chapter, a brief overview of the whole process, major findings is given. Results are discussed in the context of other research findings, implications of the study are highlighted, limitations are pointed out, and lastly, scope for further research is shown in brief.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA	<i>Analysis of Variance</i>
B.Ed.	<i>Bachelor of Education</i>
<i>df</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>
Ed.	<i>Editor</i>
Edn.	<i>Edition</i>
Eds.	<i>Editors</i>
e.g.	<i>for Example</i>
<i>et al.</i>	<i>and others</i>
Fig.	<i>Figure</i>
IBM	<i>International Business Machine</i>
I-CVI	<i>Item level Content Validity Index</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>Mean</i>
<i>N</i>	<i>Total Sample</i>
NCTE	<i>National Council for Teacher Education</i>
No.	<i>Number</i>
n.d.	<i>no date</i>
P-P Plot	<i>Percent – Percent Plot</i>
PG	<i>Post Graduate</i>
<i>p</i>	<i>Probability value</i>
p.	<i>page</i>
pp.	<i>Pages</i>
Q-Q Plot	<i>quantile-quantile Plot</i>
UG	<i>Under Graduate</i>
viz.	<i>Namely</i>
Vol.	<i>Volume</i>
Vs.	<i>Versus</i>
W.B.	<i>West Bengal</i>

CHAPTER – I INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

West Bengal (W.B.) has long occupied a special place in India in terms of higher education. One of the reasons behind this position is the interest and attitude of the general public towards higher education. At present, the interest and attitude of students towards higher education, no matter how far we are, there are many hurdles and hurdles present in front of most of the students, the financial issue has always been identified as a criterion, which has been overcome to a large extent. This reduces the financial burden of the students. Getting a scholarship is highly dependent because almost all scholarship projects are associated with the so-called institutional verification system, regardless of the scheme that the students are allowed to benefit from, they must be part of the institutional education system in one way or another. Although higher education institutions prioritize studies as the main activity, not only at present but also for a long time, many institutions abroad have arranged multiple collaborations that ensure students' proficiency and professional development as well as holistic development. Organization of awareness camps, participation in social activities, medical camps, transportation arrangements, and accommodation of hostels for student as well as various scholarships the University has a specific authority which we know as dean of student welfare. Present researchers discuss only the awareness and views of other beneficiaries especially the students and nodal officers. closely related to the scholarship related to how the institution plays its role in getting the scholarship among the multiple issues of student welfare and the institutions selected for discussion are only Colleges are mainly for teacher training. It must be mentioned here that there is an officer on behalf of the institution who is responsible for the entire process of the scholarship. Technically the individual is known as Nodal Officer/ Nodal Teacher/ Nodal Person at institute level.

1.2 Scholarships for BEd Students in West Bengal

There are scholarship resources provided by various departments of the state government for students of BEd course in West Bengal as well as scholarships provided by various departments of Indian government to the students of BEd in our state. The purpose of the financial support is to assist students in their education. Merit-based aid is provided on the base of academic performance in the last

examination passed, as well as needs base aid provides on the low-income conditions. Following are the brief details of various scholarships of the State Government and Central Government;

Notable scholarships given by various offices of the state government are Swami Vivekananda Merit cum Means Scholarship (SVMCM), which is provided by the West Bengal State Government's Higher Education Department as well as the OASIS Scholarship, which is provided by the West Bengal State Government with the help of the backward class welfare office of West Bengal. To support financially, AIKYASREE portal launched for religious minority only, under the department of minority affairs and madrasah education, govt. of West Bengal. Besides, there are Disability Scholarships for differently able students by Mass Education and Library Services Department, Government of West Bengal. A separate portal has been launched for individual scholarships offered by the state government, basically in that case notification through online system, submission of application form by students, verification process is completed mainly through online mode. On the other hand, if we look at the central government scholarship system, we can clearly see that the scholarships offered by various departments of the central government are implemented under the National Scholarship Portal, though individual terms and conditions apply there, but are completed through a single portal. The central government has created a single portal for all scholarships. On the other hand, the state government has different payment systems for different departments, which adds considerable complexity in the process of support service by the educational institute.

1.3 Awareness and Attitude towards scholarship of the Students

We need to briefly discuss why we emphasized students' awareness and attitudes towards scholarship in the present study. This study will not only discuss awareness or attitudes of the prospective teachers, but Institutional Nodal Officer awareness and viewpoint as a stakeholder in the scholarship process is also a matter of discussion. Scholarship awarding processes seemed to be offline in West Bengal since long ago. At present, except for the specially-challenged scholarship (Disability Scholarship), all other scholarships are being conducted through the online portal. Therefore, we think that students need to be sufficiently aware of the use of the Internet and the collection of various types of information. Otherwise some mistakes may be made by the students regarding the terms and conditions of the scholarship or the application

process or receiving the scholarship amount. Their attitude towards scholarship was not formed overnight. Students have come a long way in higher education through the direct or indirect experience of scholarship. That's why we the researcher considered all the students both recipients and non-recipients of scholarship in BEd under this project.

1.4 Nodal officer at Institute Level

There is a responsible person in every institution for getting scholarship that is known as Nodal Officer at institute Level. S/he is charged with this as an additional duty of the institution to support the students. Each scholarship is different in terms of target group, eligibility criteria, application process, corresponding govt. departments/offices, verification process, login technique of portal, help line etc. They are acting on a regular basis as a coordinator of several schemes between students and govt departments at different levels.

1.5 Rational of Study

Interest in higher studies is increasing among students day by day in West Bengal. On the other hand, students must undergo training to enter the teaching profession in the present context. The state government of West Bengal has organised several scholarship schemes for students to pursue their higher education. A figure will give us an idea of how much financial allocation that state government has undertaken to maintain scholarship programmes. Only SVMCM scholarship information is provided here to realise the situation of our state. In the 2009-10 financial year the budget allocation for this sector was Rs. 9.45 crore. The budget allocation in FY 2018-19 was Rs. 211.85 crore. The budget allocation for FY 2022-23 in this same sector has increased to approximately Rs. 1400 crore. As the state government of West Bengal has increased the amount allocated over time, we can definitely see that the number of students benefitting from the amount has increased over time. In the financial year 2011, the number of beneficiaries of the above mentioned amount of money was 7423 students. The number of beneficiaries increased to one lakh six hundred forty eight students in FY 2018-19. In the very last financial year i.e. 2022-23, the number of beneficiary students increased to approximately 8 lakhs. An increase in the amount of money allocated and the number of beneficiaries has increased over time which has actually reduced the financial barriers for students in higher education in West

Bengal. In the present study we are interested in reviewing the importance of increasing the number of beneficiaries and the amount allocated, emphasizing the attitudes and awareness of the beneficiaries and nodal officers involved in the entire process at institute level. We the present researchers believe that, the awareness of the beneficiaries is quite important with economic activities, which will be considered as a clear expression of their own perception towards financial responsibilities and liabilities there on. Besides, the scholarship schemes open for them will help in running the scheme more smoothly in future by expressing their views on the various pros and cons of these schemes. As we find the picture form above we have an interest to study the attitude and awareness of stakeholders towards scholarship schemes in teachers training institutes (BEd) only.

1.6 Significance of the Study

- 1) This study will be helpful to understand the attitude and awareness of the students about the several scholarship schemes available to them in BEd training in W.B.
- 2) This study will reveal the condition of the attitude towards scholarship programmes being supported by the Teacher Education Institute (TEI).
- 3) The result of this research would provide valuable information for the Nodal officers at different level to further their campaign on spreading awareness on how to deal with various issues concerning to scholarship schemes.
- 4) It is also expected that the findings of the study may give an insight towards the deep technical problems and that may enable the authorities to organise adequate programs for the welfare of the students.
- 5) This study is important for educational institutions, and for the respective Govt. departments to modify their plan of action regarding the problems faced by the stakeholders at institution and student side. The result may be used for constructive suggestions about the adequate strategy, methodology of imparting financial support and framing appropriate guideline of the scheme for such level.
- 6) The result may also give a proper direction to the decision maker on the government. The researchers are inspired to do this study to help in social consciousness among all concerned persons who deal with activity related to scholarship programme.

1.7 Statement of the Problem

On the basis of previous discussion about the financial support to continue the higher education of the students govt. have been taken several strategies like students credit card and scholarship programmes. There are very rare study have carried out in last few years on the context of teachers training in our state West Bengal. Therefore the problem may be stated as – “Scholarship as a student support service: awareness and attitudinal perspective of stakeholders in teachers training institute”.

1.8 Definition of the Important Terms Used

A. *Conceptual Definition*

- i. **Scholarship:** According to the Britanica Dictionary scholarship is an amount of money that is given by a school, an organisation, etc, to a student to help pay for the student’s education.
- ii. **Attitude:** According to Myers, (2012, p. 36) It is a favourable or unfavourable evaluative reaction toward something or someone exhibited in ones beliefs, feelings, or intended behaviour. It is a social orientation - an underlying inclination to respond to something either favourably or unfavourably.
- iii. **Awareness:** It is a state where a subject is aware of some information when that information is directly accessible to bring to bear in the way of an extensive range of behavioural actions. The concept is often the same to consciousness. The states of awareness are also connected with the states of experience therefore that the structure represent in awareness is mirrored in the structure of experience.
- iv. **Stakeholders:** Any people or groups who are positively or negatively impacted by a project, initiative, policy or organisation. They could be internal (people within your organisation) or external (people outside of your organisation).
- v. **Teacher Education Institute:** Institution established and running with the spirit to ensure the training of future teachers at school level for our society recognised by NCTE, in India.

B. *Operational Definition*

- i. **Scholarship:** In this study scholarship is the financial support from the specific department either State govt. or Central govt to the regular students of BED programme on the basis of several criteria concerned, which is disbursed yearly basis to their personal Bank Account.

ii. Attitude: In case of this project, evaluative reaction of the students towards scholarship programmes available for BEd course in W.B. All those beliefs, feelings, and intended behaviour also considered.

iii. Awareness: Knowledge, understanding and also the behavioural actions of the students regarding the different phases of scholarship programme i.e. information collection, application form, form submission, approval process, amount disbursement, eligibility criterion, etc concerning to several scholarship schemes.

iv. Stakeholders: Here, All the students of BEd programme, both recipients and non-recipients of scholarship facilities are the stakeholders. On the other hand the nodal teacher/ person/officer of the teacher education institute also directly involved with these facilities also belong as stakeholder.

v. Teacher Education Institute: All the NCTE recognised institutes of WB, which are running two year BEd programme successfully and facilitate several scholarship schemes by the Govt. to their trainees. Here, the Teacher Education Institute (TEI) is included with the Government, Government Aided and Private Institute engaging to transect the pre-service training programme also.

1.9 Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the attitude of BEd students towards scholarship schemes available in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, types of students, educational qualification, eligibility, academic discipline, caste category, types of scholarship availed for them.
- 2) To study the attitude of BEd students, towards several scholarship schemes, those are non-recipients any schemes in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category.
- 3) To study the attitude of BEd students, towards scholarship schemes, those are recipients under any scheme in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category, types of scholarship availed for them.
- 4) To measure the awareness of the BEd trainees on several issues of scholarship schemes available for them.
- 5) To measure the awareness of the trainees on scheme specific issues concerning with scholarship schemes as a part of student support service.

- 6) To understand the nature of workload of the Nodal Officers, apart from their academic activities.
- 7) To know the condition of awareness of the Nodal Officers about the procedure of several scholarship schemes.
- 8) To study the perception of Nodal Officer regarding genuine interest of recipients of different scholarship schemes.

1.10 Hypotheses

Based on the literature about the attitude and awareness of the students in relation to scholarship facilities availed within the educational institutes as a part of support to their students, the research hypotheses were as follows;

- H₀1:** There is no significant difference between BEd students of Govt. and Private Colleges in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀2:** There is no significant difference between female and male BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀3:** There is no significant difference between rural and urban BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀4:** There is no significant difference between hosteller and day scholar BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀5:** There is no significant difference between graduate and post-graduate BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀6:** There is no significant difference between eligible and ineligible BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀7:** There is no significant difference among the academic disciplines of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀8:** There is no significant difference among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.
- H₀9:** There is no significant difference among the recipients under the several scholarships in respect of their attitude towards the same.

- H₀10:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between non-recipient students of govt. and private colleges.
- H₀11:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between female and male non-recipient students.
- H₀12:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between rural and urban non-recipient students.
- H₀13:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between graduate and post graduate non-recipient students.
- H₀14:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between non-recipient hosteller and day scholar students.
- H₀15:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the academic disciplines of non-recipient students.
- H₀16:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among caste categories on non-recipient students.
- H₀17:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship recipients between govt and private college.
- H₀18:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between female and male recipients.
- H₀19:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between rural and urban recipients.
- H₀20:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between graduate and post graduate recipients.
- H₀21:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between hosteller and day scholar students.
- H₀22:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the academic disciplines of BEd students, those who are recipient of scholarship.
- H₀23:** There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the caste categories of BEd students, those who are recipient of scholarship.

H₀24: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the different recipient groups of BEd students.

1.11 Research Questions

RQ.1: What is the status of awareness about scholarship schemes among the BEd students from the perspective of different issues?

RQ.2: How much the BEd students are aware about the scheme specific issues concerning with scholarship schemes as a part of student support service at institute level in W.B.?

RQ.3: What kind of workload considered by the nodal officers at college level?

RQ.4: What is the condition of awareness of Nodal Officers at college level regarding verification and forwarding to next level?

RQ.5: What is the opinion of the nodal officer regarding the interest of students between scholarship and academic matter?

RQ.6: What is the opinion of nodal person regarding the misuse of scholarship among the students?

1.12 Delimitations of the Study

1. The study was conducted in the Districts of the southern part of West Bengal, viz. Purba Bardhaman, Purba Medinipur, North 24 praganas, Malda, Nadia, Paschim Medinipur, Hoogly, and Howrah.
2. The survey was delimited within Govt., Govt.-aided and Private BEd colleges. All the training colleges are affiliated under Babasaheb Ambedkar Education University, University of Calcutta, and University of Burdwan.
3. All the students restricted on the basis of pursuing BEd course either in first year or second year of their programme.
5. The study was delimited with four categorical variables such as types of college, gender, location, educational qualification of students, types of application, eligibility, academic discipline, caste category, and name of scholarship schemes.
6. Study was delimited with self rated questionnaires from the both kind of BEd students i.e., recipients and non-recipients of scholarship schemes.

CHAPTRE II REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Review of Literature

A report published in 2013 by the research and development initiative pvt ltd, New Delhi, on evaluation and impact assessment of post matric scholarship scheme. Where following recommendation has been mentioned to improve the management aspects of scholarship schemes; (i) there is a need to raise the awareness about the Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme through print and electronic media. This would help stimulate demand for higher of households from minority communities currently not going for higher secondary and higher education. (ii) the school/institution is the major source of information about the Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme and the teacher plays a critical role in disseminating the related information. However, the school/institution as well as the teacher is not provided with detailed information about the scheme, particularly the selection process and criteria, cut-off scores for preparing the final list of selected students. Procedures of processing applications (including preference and selection criteria) and sanctioning of scholarships need to be detailed out and communicated to schools and the beneficiaries. Not only that, this information can be pasted in websites of Ministry of Minority Affairs and the concerned state government departments. This would make the management of Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme transparent and accountable. (iii) There is a need to amend the eligibility criteria for availing the Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme. The minimum requirement of family income should be taken as the sole eligibility criterion for applying for the Post-Matric Scholarship. (iv) The policy of automatic renewal of Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme may be adopted within a given education cycle. (v) More efforts are required to make management of post-matric scholarship scheme IT intensive, particularly making online submission of application and transfer of post-matric scholarship money to the bank accounts of schools/institutions and beneficiaries a reality. (vi) The Post-Matric Scholarship Scheme rates, particularly the maintenance allowance rates for both hostellers and day scholars need to be revised. (vii) Finally, there is an urgent need to improve the frequency of disbursement of post-matric scholarship, preferably making it monthly.

Biswas (2018) explored that, SC and ST students are not aware properly regarding govt. scholarship schemes at under graduate and post graduate level in West Bengal.

But, no differences were found between UG and PG level of students. Caste category and gender of the students was no effect on their awareness regarding government scholarship schemes. Here, researcher conducted survey by the using of questionnaire on two hundred and four samples. Study recommended increasing awareness of scholarship among the students through advertising on television, newspapers, radio. All the institutes need to promote such kind of scheme among the students within their campus also.

Samsujjaman (2018) conducted a study on the awareness of UG and PG students towards different government scholarship only for schedule caste and scheduled tribe community. Study was focused on students at college and university level of WB. With descriptive survey approach two hundred and four samples were considered. Data were analysed by use of mean, SD and t test also. Study revealed that, there was a lacking on awareness about the scholarship schemes among the scheduled caste and scheduled tribe students in WB.

Correspondent of Hindustan Times (2018) reported that, the majority of students from Jammu and Kashmir, who avail a special scholarship by the Central Government to pursue higher education across India, have assumed living outside their native place has transformed their knowledge and attitude towards people from other parts of the country. The survey was conducted by Mumbai's Tata Institute of Social Science (TISS). That assignment was tasked by the Union Human Resource Development ministry and the All India Council for Technical Education to assess the Prime Minister's Special Scholarship Scheme for students from Jammu and Kashmir only. The TISS was asked to evaluate the scheme, and find out problems faced by the students and reasons behind dropouts. More than 2,670 students considered here as sample. Most of the students, said they would leave their state to pursue further education and look for jobs outside. Study also reported that, students were able to explore fresh lifestyles and new situations. They also believed that the scheme helped in improvement in self-knowledge, thoughts and behaviour, confidence level, increasing taste for diverse food, learning different languages and culture, among others.

Lama (2019) conducted an evaluative study of post-matric scholarship on tribal students in Darjeeling municipality. Objective was to find out the support of post-matric scholarship in the development of education in ST students. Descriptive as

well as exploratory method was adopted there. Both, primary and secondary data were collected by survey on target group and the office of the Back Ward Class Welfare & Tribal Development. Survey conducted on 150 samples through simple random process. Survey found that, guidelines of the scheme were not following properly by the students. Study reported that, post-matric scholarship is very beneficial to the economically poor students for continuation of their higher studies. In this researcher recommended that, there is a need of wide and effective publicity before the starting of every session. DWO will ensure the benefit of the post-matric scholarship should be provided during the running session. More transparency is needed in the disbursement of funds in scholarship. A vital complain also reported there that, Tribal students were not getting their payments in proper time.

Indo Asian News Service (2021) reported in India TV, highlighted the issue of scam in scholarship scheme. While the Bihar government has been facing criticism over several scams in its 16-year tenure, the latest one has been detected in Darbhanga by the state minority welfare department involving scholarships to three hundred and seventy six students in the district. The officials of the minority welfare department reported that three hundred and seventy six students have fraudulently taken scholarship of Rs 30,000 each using fake admission papers in a particular university in Hyderabad. During the verification of application form, it was found that the alleged students have used the name of the university to claim the scholarship grant. Next, they contacted the students who have taken the scholarship. It was also found that the maximum of these students, one hundred and thirty seven, belong to Darbhanga district. Out of them, fourteen students appeared before the department and claimed that the fraudulent act was done by the employees of a cyber cafe. They have also asked students to reverse the amount to the department within ten days otherwise have to face legal notice.

Mandal, Guha and Banerjee (2021) conducted a descriptive survey to find out the attitude towards post-matric scholarship and their education of higher secondary students (N=450) in west Bengal. Self made standardised questionnaire was used by them to collect data. This study found that, gender and location of the students are determinant factor of the attitude towards post-matric scholarship in West Bengal. Girls have high attitude than the boys in respect of attitude towards scholarship schemes. Rural students shows higher attitude than the urban students regarding

scholarship programme. But, study also stated that, no difference was there between recipient and non recipients of post-matric scholarship schemes in terms of their attitude towards education.

Santosh and Bora (2021) reported in their study on the awareness about different scholarship schemes among the students of Assam Agricultural University. Two hundred forty undergraduate students were participated by stratified random sampling technique from the college of agriculture, and college of community science. Data collected through questionnaire in online Google form. Items in questionnaire were fixed with the opinion of expert in relevant area. Results of this study indicated that, students had medium level of awareness on different scholarship schemes. Analysis indicated that, female were more aware in respect of gender. In terms of religion Hindus were more aware than other groups. English medium students were more aware than the Assamese and Hindi medium students. They reported also the awareness was more on state merit scholarship than national talent scholarship. Around three percent students were aware about the provision for financial support to the economically backward students of Assam Agricultural University. Study recommended encouraging students to take benefits of scholarship in higher education.

Bodh (2022) mentioned that, in Himachal Pradesh a matter pertaining to wrongful and illegal disbursement and misappropriation of post-matric scholarship scheme to SC, ST and OBC students, the High Court has directed the CBI to expedite the process of completion of investigation and file the charge sheets at the earliest. Earlier in the high court had on April 4, took note of the submissions made by the counsel for CBI that, out of 266 private institutions, 28 were involved in the alleged scholarship scam. The petitioner has further alleged that the enquiry report revealed that the huge scam of scholarship money was misappropriated. Apart from the educational institutions within the state, scores of educational institutions stationed in other states of India, were also involved in this scam.

Das (2022, November 02) mentioned in India Today-North East, daily news that, the name of the Ishan Uday Scholarship Scheme and the central government's ministry of minority development for meritorious students from minority communities, a huge fraud cycle has been detected in Assam's Barpeta district. A ferocious circle has dishonestly siphoned off crores of rupees in the name of fake students of some

colleges in the Assam. Barpeta police have already arrested two accused persons in connection with the particular scam in the name of the Ishan Uday Scholarship Scheme. Barpeta Additional Superintendent of Police Pradeep Saikia told reporters at a press conference. Speaking to the media, the Additional Superintendent of Police said, "Upon interrogation, it was revealed that the duo has siphoned around Rs 78,000 in the year 2018 and in 2022 the duo has faked around three hundred students under the minority development scheme in the name of siphoning scholarship money", the Additional Superintendent added. Notably, the said money siphoned in the name of a scholarship in 2022 is currently under investigation and will be shared shortly. It is to be noted that students who pass the Higher Secondary Examination with seventy five per cent marks are given a scholarship of about Rs 60,000 per year in Assam.

A study conducted by Ahmed, et. al. (2022) in Pakistan, to find out the impact of scholarship on student success in the University of Turbat. Where, researchers argued that, access to higher education is poor in the disadvantaged areas of Pakistan. Both the federal and provincial governments of Pakistan have initiated several scholarship schemes for undergraduate students in underprivileged areas. They stated that, short to medium-term impact of a need-based scholarship programme was effective only for male students in improving their academic performance. Study also revealed that scholarship schemes not only helped the recipients to maintain higher education but supported their siblings' education, purchasing books and other reading materials. However, it was also mentioned that, many students exploit their stipends for buying assets.

Times News Network (2023) published about subsequent the dismissal of six government officials from service for their suspected involvement in the rupees thirty nine crore in post-matric scheduled caste scholarship scam after being indicated by a departmental inquiry, the Pujab government on Friday recommended a further in-depth probe into this scam by the Vigilance Bureau (VB). All these include four from the department of social justice, empowerment and minorities and two from the finance department. Minister in charge of the concerned department said all the events took place in 2019 where discrepancies of rupees fifty crore were detected. During the departmental probe, it came to fore that there was no proof of the remaining amount of rupees thirty nine crore since this amount was disbursed to several dummy colleges.

According to the opinion of principal (2023), Dr B. R Ambedkar College, Tehatta, Nadia, W.B. there were found ninety nine fake application of minority scholarship in 2022-23 session. All those application were submitted along with fake income certificates and fake payment receipts of that college. During the verification of four thousand applications submitted in that college, few of application suspected as false by the authority. College authority lodged complains to the local police station for detail investigation. As per the statement of college all the fake applicants were from the murshidabad district. Authority of college also mentioned that, there was a big racket on scholarship matter in the WB.

Web desk of India Today (2 March, 2023) reported taht, the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) has discovered serious anomalies in 13 out of 22 educational institutions that are under investigation in connection with the Rs 250 crore scholarship scam. CBI officials said that investigations showed that these 13 universities accepted scholarships in the names of roughly 2,000 fake students. They are yet to examine the remaining institutions' accounts and other paperwork. The CBI investigated the documents, accounts, and data it obtained from computers and other related material of these institutions in Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, and Chandigarh and found that scholarship funds had been siphoned off and awards had been given to students who either didn't exist or had left the institutions.

Tiwary (2023) reported in The Indian Express that, the Enforcement Directorate (ED) conducted searches at twenty locations across six districts in Uttar Pradesh in connection with a case of money laundering against some educational institutions which fraudulently availed of post-matriculation government scholarships meant for students from minority, dalit and tribal communities. The agency said its investigations have revealed that scholarships worth Rs seventy five crore have been availed of by these institutions and some of the scholarships had been taken against bank accounts of seven-year-olds. According to the ED, the central and state governments provide various scholarships to facilitate the education of SC, ST and physically handicapped candidates. Further, some scholarships are meant for minority candidates and students from economically weaker sections (EWS).

Saha (2023) mentioned in his article in Bartaman daily news that, chief minister of West Bengal launched swami Vivekananda merit cum means scholarship to provide financial assistance to students at school level and higher education also. The state

government of West Bengal does not want financial scarcity to become an obstacle in the higher education of students. The state government has reduced the eligibility criteria from 75 % to 60% in order to provide scholarship opportunities to more students. At present the estimated number of beneficiaries of this scheme is near about eight lack students for whom the amount allocated is approximately rupees 1400 crore in 2022-23 financial year.

2.2 Critical Appraisal of the Reviews

In current times there has been increased attention to the student support services at the higher education institutions of India. Scholarship is gaining importance in educational institutions as a student support service. Like other states, higher educational institutions in West Bengal are showing great interest in scholarship. Students in higher education in West Bengal are benefiting from the benefits of scholarships provided by various departments of the state government as well as central government. Though the review of the above articles, the present researchers have come to the conclusion that, the extent of scholarship awareness among the students and the students towards scholarship, in addition to finding out the same among the officers who are entrusted in the process at institute level, the issue of their perception by the college authorities will also be important as the subject of the present study. From the literature review we mainly see two types of articles. First is a type of essay that is related to scholarships in different states of India and their benefits among the students in school and higher education level. We also see the lack of awareness among the students and the lack of promotion within the system existed in several scholarship schemes. Just as lack of awareness among students to get financial benefits, a handful of people exploit this ignorance and get involved in various types of financial corruption. Although research related to scholarship schemes has been done in other states of India, West Bengal has seen its lack in a big way. Currently, scholarship schemes in teacher education are inadequate in terms of the extent to which students are aware of or their attitudes towards the scheme of scholarship. Simultaneously, perception of nodal person or officer regarding the process or matter of scholarship also not covered in very recently in WB.

CHAPTER – III METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design: In this project investigators used multi-method design of research. Present researcher attempted to study the attitude and awareness of BEd students regarding several schemes of scholarship available for them in West Bengal. Thus, keeping objectives of this study, descriptive survey method was used in this part. Similarly, present researchers also attempted to realise the attitude and awareness of Nodal officers / Persons, who engaged at institute level regarding the process of application form submission, verification, & forwarding of scholarship schemes to respective portal. Thus keeping objectives of this part qualitative analysis also made.

3.2 Population: Prospective teachers, who are pursuing their Bachelor of Education (BEd) programme in West Bengal and the all those Nodal Teacher or Officer or Person, who are liable to their institute as well as to their students in terms of all the activities associated with scholarship schemes and as a part of students support service.

3.3 Sample: In this study, eight districts from the southern part of West Bengal were considered at the starting of sample selection. Here, the researchers adopted the simple random sampling techniques. Seventeen teachers training institutes were identified randomly to fix the sample unit. From those unites researchers considered BEd students (N=1112) randomly. Simultaneously, fifteen Nodal officers were taken from those teachers training institute concerned. Following table (3.1) shows the distribution of sample. The table 3.1 shows that, in respect of types of BEd college out of 1112 students, 640 students were govt (57.55 %) and 472 students were private (42.45 %). In respect of gender, out of 1112 students, 666 were female (59.89 %) and 446 were male (40.11 %). In respect of location, 703 were rural (63.22 %) and 409 were urban (36.78 %). In respect of nature of application, out of 1112 students, 205 were hosteller (18.44 %) and 907 were day scholar (81.56%). Out of 1112 students, 307 were under-graduate (27.61 %) and 805 were post-graduate (72.39 %) in terms of students educational qualification. In respect of eligibility to apply in scholarship schemes out of 1112 students, 938 were eligible (84.35 %) and 174 were not eligible (15.65 %). If we found the groups of academic discipline, out of 1112 students, 397 were language (35.70 %), 290 were science (26.08%), 417

were social science (37.5%) and only 8 were from engineering & technology (0.72%). In case of caste categories out of 1112 students, 497 were unreserved (44.69%), 298 were schedule caste (26.80%), 64 were schedule tribe (5.76%) and 253 were OBC (22.75%). If we look at the schemes by which students were benefitted financially, out of 1112 students, 782 were under SVMCM (70.32%), 115 were under OASIS (10.34%), 39 were under AIKYASREE (3.51%), and only 2 were under the National Scholarship Portal (0.18%).

Table 3.1 Sample Distribution

Sl. No.	Categorical Variables	Variations	Frequency	Percent
1	TYPES OF COLLEGE	Govt.	640	57.55
		Private	472	42.45
	Total		1112	100
2	GENDER	Female	666	59.89
		Male	446	40.11
	Total		1112	100
3	LOCATION	Rural	703	36.78
		Urban	409	18.44
	Total		1112	100
4	NATURE OF APPLICATION	Hosteller	205	27.61
		Day Scholar	907	72.39
	Total		1112	100
5	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	Graduate	307	16.90
		Post-Graduate	805	59.89
	Total		1112	100
6	ELIGIBILITY	Eligible	938	84.35
		Ineligible	174	15.65
	Total		1112	100
7	ACADEMIC DISCIPLINE	Language	397	35.70
		Science	290	27.08
		Social Science	417	37.50
		Engineering & Technology	08	0.72
	Total		1112	100
8	CASTE CATEGORIES	Unreserved	497	44.69
		SC	298	26.80
		ST	64	5.76
		OBC	253	22.75
	Total		1112	100
9	NAME OF SCHOLARSHIP	SVMCM	782	70.32
		OASIS	115	10.34
		AIKYASREE	39	3.51
		NSP	02	0.18
		NON-RECIPIENT	174	15.65
	Total		1112	100

Figure 3.1 West Bengal: The Area of Study

But, 174 students were under the group of non-recipients of any kind of scholarship (15.65%) during the teachers training programme of prospective teacher in W.B. Following figures shows the proportion of samples in respect of several categorical variables.

Fig. 3.2 Types of College

Fig. 3.3 Gender of Students

Fig. 3.4 Locale of Students

Fig. 3.5 Types of Application

Fig. 3.6 Educational Institution

Fig. 3.7 Types of Eligibility

Fig. 3.8 Academic Discipline of students

Fig. 3.9 Caste Categories of Students

Fig. 3.10 Students under different Schemes

3.4 Variables

3.4.1 Major Variable: In this study major variables are following;

- (i) Attitude and
- (ii) Awareness of stakeholders about scholarship

3.4.2 Categorical Variables: The study was conducted with four different contextual situations like, location of the schools, gender, teaching experiences and educational qualifications of the geography teacher in Bengali medium schools of West Bengal. Categorical variables were follows;

1. Types of BEd college (Govt. & Private),
2. Gender of students (Male & Female),
3. Location of college (Rural & Urban),
4. Nature of application (Hosteller & Day Scholar),
5. Educational Qualification (Graduate & Post-graduate),
6. Eligibility (Eligible & not eligible),
7. Academic discipline (Language, Science, Social science, & Engineering-technology)
8. Caste category (Unreserved, Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe, & Other Backward Caste)
9. Name of scholarship (SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE, NSP, & Non Recipients of any scholarship)

3.5 Tools Used in the Study

Three research tools were used to fulfil the requirement of this study, which are bellows;

3.5.1: Questionnaire to measure Attitude of Students:

To measure the attitude of students towards scholarship schemes a self made Likert type questionnaire (Appendix-I) has standardised by the researchers. There were thirteen items in the whole self rated questionnaire. Out of thirteen items, nine items were positive (Items_1,_2,_3,_4,_5,_6,_8,_10,_13,) and four were negative (Item_7,_9,_11, &_12) in nature. Responses were scored with strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree in 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 for positive items respectively. On the other hand scoring was reversed in case of negative items. The range of obtained score varies from 13 to 65.

Content validity of the tool was established after the discussion with expert from the particular field. Internal consistency of the thirteen items also calculated to check the reliability of the tool. The Cronbach's Alpha was 0.72 on the sample of 130 students in this study. Value of cronbach's alpha indicates a high level of internal consistency of the items within the questionnaire of measuring attitude towards scholarship schemes available for BEd programme in W.B.

Table 3.2 Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	130	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	130	100.0

Table 3.3 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.72	13

3.5.2: Questionnaire to measure Awareness of Students:

To measure the awareness of students about several scholarship schemes researchers develop a multiple choice answer type questionnaire (Appendix-II). This is the part, which is consisted with ten items concerning to the several aspects of scholarship purposes. First item (Item_1) is for knowing the particular scholarship schemes received by the students on that academic year or in the previous year. Next four items (Item_2 to Item_5) are placed to know about the scheme specific awareness of the students. Last five items (Item_6 to Item_10) were framed to determine the general awareness of students regarding scholarship programme. One of the options is correct and others are wrong. Score 1 (One) is given for choosing correct option, and 0 (Zero) is given for choosing wrong option. The range of obtained score varies from 0 to 9.

3.5.3: Semi Structured Interview Schedule:

To realise the attitude and awareness of nodal officer/ nodal teacher at institute level, researchers develop a semi-structured open ended interview schedule (Appendix- III). This is consisted with four items. To study their in-depth thoughts and feelings

sometimes more questions allied to the issue were asked by the interviewer. All the information given by those nodal officer/ teacher/ person are analysed qualitatively.

3.6 Statistical Techniques Employed

3.6.1 t-test: As the objectives of the present study demand to compare attitude of BED students in respect of their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, eligibility, academic discipline, caste categories, name of schemes variations. For this purpose t-test has been employed to find out the significant difference of the types of college variation (govt. Vs. private), gender variation (Male Vs. Female), location variation (Rural Vs. Urban), nature of application variation (Hosteller Vs. Day scholar) Qualification variation (Under-graduate Vs. Post-graduate). Before applying t-test the investigators made sure that the data were normally distributed (See table 3.4). The basic statistics i.e., mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis was computed for each group.

3.6.2 ANOVA: As the objectives of the present study demand to compare attitude of BED students in respect of their academic discipline, caste categories, name of schemes variations. For this purpose ANOVA has been employed to find out the significant difference of the caste variation (UR, SC, ST, OBC), variation in discipline (Language, Science, Social Sc., Engineering & technology), Variations in schemes (SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE, NSP). Before applying ANOVA the investigators made sure that the data were normally distributed.

3.6.3 Effect Sizes: Here, present researcher interpreted each analysis with respect to their null hypothesis. Where interpretations not only considered by mentioning statistical significance existed or not, effect sizes of each analysis also done i.e., Cohen's *d*, and Eta Squared for t-test, and ANOVA respectively.

3.6.4 Percentage Analysis: In this report such research questions were answered through the Percentage analysis. It was appropriate to know how many of the participants gave a particular answer. Generally, it is reported when the responses have discrete categories. This means that the responses fall in different categories, such as aware or not-aware, different caste group, and scholarship scheme etc.

3.7 Presentation of Quantitative Data

Nature of data is following in respect of total students' attitude, Attitude of non-recipient students and Attitude of recipient students in scholarship programme.

Table 3.4 Descriptive Statistics for Major Variables with respect to Total Sample

Attitude towards scholarship	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
	1112	46.5306	.14146	4.7173	-.144	.073	-.105	.147

From the Table 3.4, it is found that, mean score of students (N= 1112) is 46.53, in respect of attitude towards scholarship. Standard deviation of the attitude score is 4.71. Table 3.4 also shows in case of students attitude, skewness is 0.144 and kurtosis is 0.105, both are negative, indicating that the data were slightly left-skewed and thinner tails (platykurtic) compared to a normal distribution. Applying the rule of thumb of dividing each value by its standard error for attitude, gives 1.97 & 0.71 for skewness and kurtosis respectively both fit within ± 3 limits, suggesting that the departure from normality is not extreme (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2020). Graphical presentation of the normal distribution of attitude scores are presented in the following figures (3.11 & 3.12)

Figure 3.11 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in Histogram

Figure 3.12 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in Q-Q Plot

From the above presented graphs it is seen that, histogram (Fig. 3.11), is looks nearly bell shape, Q-Q plot (Fig.3.12), as most of scores lie on the straight line. Thus it can be concluded that, the score of attitude of recipient is normally distributed.

Table 3.5 Descriptive Statistics for Major Variables with respect to Sample_Scholarship Non-recipient

Attitude of non- recipients towards scholarship	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
	174	44.1609	.35649	4.70241	-.386	.184	-.094	.366

From the Table 3.5, it is found that, mean score of students (N= 174) is 44.16, in respect of attitude towards scholarship. Standard deviation of the attitude score is 4.70. Table 3.4 also shows in case of students attitude, skewness is 0.386 and kurtosis is 0.094, both are negative, indicating that the data were slightly left-skewed and thinner tails (platykurtic) compared to a normal distribution. The ZSK was calculated as -2.10 (-.386 divided by .184, Table 3.5) and similarly, the ZKU was calculated as -.257 (-.094 divided by .366, Table 3.5). Both value of skewness and kurtosis are fit within +3 to -3 limits, suggesting that the departure from normality is not extreme (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2020). Hence, the data is found to be normality distributed with respect to ZSK and ZKU. Graphical

presentations of the normal distribution of attitude scores are presented in the following figures (3.13, 3.14, 3.15, & 3.16).

Figure 3.13 Distributions of scores in attitude of non-recipient students in Histogram

Figure 3.14 Distributions of scores in attitude of non-recipient students in Q-Q Plot

Figure 3.15 Distributions of scores in attitude of non-recipient students in P-P Plot

Figure 3.16 Distributions of scores in attitude of non-recipient students in Box Plot

From the above presented graphs it is seen that, histogram (Fig. 3.13), is looks nearly bell shape, Q-Q plot and P-P plot (Fig.3.14 & 3.15), as most of scores lie on the straight line. Furthermore the Box plot (Fig.3.16) shows no significant outlier or even outlier also. Thus it can be concluded that, the score of attitude of recipient is normally distributed.

Table 3.6 Descriptive Statistics for Major Variables with respect to Sample_Scholarship Recipients

Attitude of recipients towards scholarship	N	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
	938	46.9701	.35649	4.70241	-.071	.080	-.260	.160

From the Table 3.6, it is found that, mean score of recipient students (N= 938) is 46.97, in respect of attitude towards scholarship. Standard deviation of the attitude score is 4.70. Table 3.6 also shows in case of students attitude, skewness is 0.071 and kurtosis is 0.080, both are negative, indicating that the data were slightly left-skewed and thinner tails (platykurtic) compared to a normal distribution. Applying the rule of thumb, dividing each value of skewness and kurtosis by the standard error, gives 0.89 & 1.63 for skewness and kurtosis respectively. Both value of skewness and kurtosis are fit within +3 to -3 limits, (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2020), suggesting that the departure from normality is not extreme.

Graphical presentation of the normal distribution of attitude scores are presented in the following figures (3.17, 3.18, 3.19 & 3.20)

Figure 3.17 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in Histogram

Figure 3.18 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in Q-Q Plot

Figure 3.19 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in P-P Plot

Figure 3.20 Distributions of scores in attitude of recipient students in Box Plot

From the graphs it is seen that, histogram (Fig. 3.17), is looks nearly bell shape, Q-Q plot and P-P plot (Fig.3.18 & 3.19), as most of scores lie on the straight line. Furthermore the Box plot (Fig.3.20) shows no significant outlier or even outlier also. Thus it can be concluded that, the score of attitude of recipient is normally distributed.

3.8 Presentation of Qualitative Data

Earlier in this chapter it was report researchers already mentioned that, the multi method approach was adopted to fulfill the both quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study. Here, all the aspects involved with qualitative method are described in brief, which is following;

3.8.1 Approach: To address the phenomena involved in this study qualitatively, it was decided that, to focus on the identification of main theme from the data given by nodal officer who were considered throughout the study as one of the participant and also significant in this scheme of scholarship programme continuation. The data given by the nodal officer considered as helpful one to understand the meaning of the data. Therefore, the purpose, thematic analysis was considered appropriate to explore the meaning of data given by the nodal officer.

3.8.2 Participants: Seventeen teacher education colleges were included to collect data as the principal agreed to allow the collection of data for the study. However, out of seventeen nodal officers two of them declined to provide data from their end. Naturally, the number of nodal officers decreases to fifteen as participants of this study. The nodal officer/persons with their type of college, actual designation and gender are given on the next page (Table 3.7).

Table 3.7 Nature of Participants in Qualitative study

Sl. No.	Types of College	Designation Of Nodal Person	Gender
1	Government	Assistant Professor	Male
2	Government	Assistant Professor	Male
3	Government	Assistant Professor	Female
4	Government Aided	Assistant Professor	Female
5	Government Aided	Assistant Professor	Male
6	Government Aided	Assistant Professor	Male
7	Government Aided	Assistant Librarian	Male
8	Government Aided	Lower Division Clerk	Male
9	Government Aided	State Aided College Teacher	Male
10	Private	Office Staff	Male
11	Private	Librarian	Male
12	Private	Office Staff	Male
13	Private	Office Staff	Male
14	Private	Assistant Professor	Male
15	Private	Assistant Professor	Male
16	Private	Assistant Professor	Male
17	Private	Assistant Professor	Male

Table 3.7 shows that, nature of the college is Government, Government aided, as well as private also. It is also observed from the table that, the nodal person are borne having either male or female belong to the designation which is spread across the teaching and non-teaching staff.

3.8.3 Procedure: All the outset of the interaction with the nodal person of concerned college the principal investigator introduces himself maintaining the interview protocol and briefly explained that the intention of the interview is to talk to the nodal officer regarding the activities related to scholarship those are to be carried out by nodal officer and other allied issues associated with scholarship programme. Semi structured interview schedule was developed to get the information from the participants. The interview session was recorded through voice recording in cell phone with the consent of nodal officer. Only three interviews with nodal officer were conducted telephonically.

3.8.4 Techniques: Audio recording collected from the nodal person. Audio were transcribed by the principal investigator. Initial thoughts and opinions of the nodal person were noted down. Transcribed data were read repeatedly. Audio recordings were listened frequently also. Pertinent codes/ concepts were identified with the research questions. Codes were clubbed within the category. Finally, theme was derived from the analysis.

CHAPTER – IV ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

4.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, the research methodology employ by the researchers to carry out the objectives of the study was discussed. This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data collected based on the structure of reference of this report.

The major objective of the present study was to find out the attitude and awareness of the BEd students regarding the scholarship schemes available for them. As well as the Perception of the Nodal Officer/ Person involved at institute level to serve this assignment as a part of student support service in West Bengal. The present research consisted with seven objectives. To fulfill those objectives and twenty four hypotheses and four research questions were framed to find out the attitude and awareness factors concerning with the several scholarship schemes of major stakeholders.

As mentioned prior, the present chapter deals with the several analysis and interpretation of the data. This section of analysis pertaining to the scores received from the respondents students in BEd programme (N = 1112) having different demographic characteristics and nodal person at institute level. This section involves three different sub-sections. The first sub-section display the results of t-test and ANOVA to find out the significance of difference between the groups of college types, gender, locale, nature of applicant, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste categories, name of scholarship in respect of students attitude towards scholarship schemes. The second sub-section shows the results of percentage analysis to find out the awareness of students regarding scholarship schemes. The third sub-section shows the result of qualitative analysis of nodal person regarding scholarship as a student support service at institute level. The raw data were tabulated in MS Excel 2007 and analyses of data done through SPSS 20.0 version.

4.2 Objective wise Analysis of Data

For the analysis of data with respect to each objective, several inferential statistical measures were adopted such as t-test and ANOVA. Inferential statistics is considered here to use the laws of probability to make inferences about populations based on sample

data (Johnson & Christensen, 2012). Use of inferential statistics is based upon the assumption of random sampling.

4. A Inferential Statistics Used

4.2.1 Objective 1: To study the attitude of BEd students towards scholarship schemes available in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of applicant, educational qualification, eligibility, academic discipline, caste category, types of scholarship availed for them.

To fulfill the above objective, null hypotheses **H₀₁** to **H₀₉** were formulated and tested which are follows;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between BEd students of Govt. and Private Colleges in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.1 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd students_types of college

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Types of College	Govt.			
			Private	640	46.95
		472	45.97	4.53	

From the Table 4.1, it is observed that, there is slight difference in mean scores of students in attitude towards scholarship schemes in Govt BEd college ($M = 46.95$, $SD = 4.81$, $N = 640$) and Private BEd college ($M = 45.97$, $SD = 4.53$, $N = 472$). Whether this mean difference is statistically significant or not; further independent samples t-test was done.

Table 4.2 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of BEd students in respect of Types of college

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Types of College (Govt. vs Private)		2.15	.143	3.43	1110	.001

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.2) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 2.15 and corresponding p value is .143 ($p > .05$) for the variations in terms of

types of college. Here, for attitude the variability is same in types of college, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.2 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between the students of Govt and private BEd college, the calculated $t_{(1110)}$ value is 3.43 and p value is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, ' t ' is significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is rejected and it can be said that, the students of Govt BEd college are significantly different from the students of Private BEd college with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, modest effect size ($d = 0.21$) is found between the students of govt. and private college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between female and male BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.3 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd students_gender

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Gender				
	Female	Male	666	46.14	4.57
			446	47.12	4.87

From the Table 4.3 it is observed that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of female students ($M = 46.14$, $SD = 4.57$, $N = 666$) and male students ($M = 47.12$, $SD = 4.87$, $N = 446$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.4 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of BEd students in respect of gender

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender (Female vs. Male)		3.27	.071	3.42*	1110	.001

(* Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.4) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 3.27 and corresponding p value is .071 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of

gender. Here, for attitude the variability is same in gender, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.4 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between female and male BEd students, the calculated $t_{(1110)}$ value is 3.42 and p value is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at .05 level. So, H_02 is rejected and it can be said that, the female students are significantly different from the male students with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, modest effect size ($d = 0.21$) is found between the female and male students of B.Ed college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between rural and urban BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.5 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd students_locale

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Locale	Rural			
			Urban	703	46.85
		Urban	409	45.98	5.0

From the Table 4.5, it is observed that, there is a slight difference in the mean scores of rural BEd students ($M = 46.85$, $SD = 4.5$, $N = 703$) and urban ($M = 45.98$, $SD = 5.0$, $N = 409$). Whether, this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.6 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of BEd students in respect of locale

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Locale (Rural vs. Urban)	Equal variances assumed	2.96	.086	2.99*	1110	.003

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.6) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 2.96 and corresponding p value is .086 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of locale. Here, for attitude the variability is same in locale, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.6 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between rural and urban BEd student, the calculated $t_{(1110)}$ value is 2.99 and p value is .003 ($p < .05$). Hence, 't' is significant at .05 level. So, H_03 is rejected and it can be said that, the rural students are significantly different from the urban students with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, Weak effect size ($d = 0.18$) is found between the rural and urban students of BEd college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between hosteller and day scholar BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.7 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd students_nature of applicants

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Types of Students	Hosteller			
			Day Scholar	205	47.91
		907	46.23	4.72	

From the Table 4.7, it is observed that, there is a slight difference in the mean scores in attitude of hosteller ($M = 47.91$, $SD = 4.46$, $N = 205$) and day scholar ($M = 46.23$, $SD = 4.72$, $N = 907$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.8 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of BEd students in respect of nature of applicants

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Nature of Applicants (Hosteller vs. Day Scholar)		1.33	.249	4.67*	1110	.001

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.8) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 1.33 and corresponding p value is .249 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of nature of applicants. Here, for attitude the variability is same in nature of applicant, thus equal variances can be assumed.

This Table 4.8 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between hosteller and day scholar BEd students, the calculated $t_{(1110)}$ value is 4.67 and p is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, 't' is significant at .05 level. So, H_04 is rejected and it can be said that, the hosteller are significantly different from the day scholar with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, modest effect size ($d = 0.37$) is found between the hosteller and day scholar students of BEd college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference between graduate and post graduate BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.9 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd students_Educational Qualification

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Educational Qualification				
	Graduate		307	46.22	4.47
	Post Graduate		805	46.65	4.80

The Table 4.9 shows that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude of graduate students ($M = 46.22$, $SD = 4.47$, $N = 307$) and post graduate students ($M = 46.65$, $SD = 4.8$, $N = 805$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.10 Independent Samples 't' test; attitude of BEd student in respect of educational qualification

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Educational Qualification (Graduate vs. Post Graduate)	Equal variances not assumed	4.61	.032	1.41#	590.97	.160

(# Not Significant at .05 level)

The Table 4.10 shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the calculated F is 4.61 and corresponding p value is .032 ($p < .05$) for the variations in

respect of educational qualification. Here, for attitude the variability is not same in educational qualification, thus equal variances not assumed.

Table 4.10 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between graduate and post graduate BEd student, the calculated $t_{(590,97)}$ value is 1.36 and p is .160 ($p > .05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is not rejected. It can be said that, the graduate students are not significantly different from the post graduate student with respect to attitude. Here, Weak effect size ($d = 0.09$) is found between the graduate and post-graduate students of BEd college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀6: There is no significant difference between eligible and ineligible BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.11 Group Statistics of attitude of BEd student_eligibility

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Eligibility	Eligible	933	46.95	4.61
		Ineligible	179	44.34	4.69

The Table 4.11 shows that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude of eligible students ($M = 46.95$, $SD = 4.61$, $N = 933$) and ineligible students ($M = 44.34$, $SD = 4.69$, $N = 179$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.12 Independent Samples 't' test; attitude of BEd student in respect of eligibility in Scholarship

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Eligibility (Eligible vs Ineligible)		.001	.98	6.92*	1110	.001

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.12) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the calculated F value is .001 and corresponding p value is .98 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of eligibility. Here, for attitude the variability is the same, in eligibility, thus equal variances can be assumed.

This Table 4.12 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between eligible and ineligible B.Ed student, the calculated $t_{(1110)}$ value is 6.92 and p is .001 ($p <$

.05). Hence, ' t ' is significant at .05 level. So, H_{06} is rejected. It can be said that, the eligible students are significantly different from the ineligible BEd students with respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, moderate effect size ($d = 0.56$) is found between those students who are eligible and not eligible to get scholarship in BEd college in terms of their attitude towards scholarship programme through Cohen's (1988) measure.

H₀₇: There is no significant difference among the academic disciplines of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.13 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd student_several academic discipline

	Academic Discipline	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Language	397	46.69	4.5
	Science	290	46.60	5.03
	Social Science	417	46.35	4.72
	Engineering & Technology	8	45.75	4.03
Total		1112	46.53	4.72

Fig. 4.1 Means Plot_attitude of students_academic discipline

It is observed from the above (Table 4.13) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their academic disciplines i.e, language (M= 46.69, SD= 4.5, N= 397), science (M= 46.60, SD= 5.03, N= 290), social science

(M= 46.35, SD= 4.72, N= 417), engineering & technology (M= 45.75, SD= 4.03, N= 8). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.14 Oneway ANOVA test for attitude of BEd students_academic discipline wise

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	30.88	3	10.30	.46	.71 [#]	.001	.144
Within Group	24692.079	1108	22.29				
Total	24722.960	1111					

([#]Not Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.14 shows that, the calculated F (3, 1108) is .46 and p is .71(p > .05). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H₀₇ is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no significant difference among the academic disciplines of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, very small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.001) is found among the groups of academic discipline of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

H₀₈: There is no significant difference among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes.

Table 4.15 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd student_Caste category wise

	Caste Categories	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Unreserved	497	46.45	4.8
	Scheduled Caste	298	46.34	4.46
	Scheduled Tribe	64	46.69	4.76
	Other Backward Caste	253	45.87	4.77
Total		1112	46.53	4.72

Fig. 4.2 Means Plot_attitude of students_caste categories

It is observed from the above (Table 4.15) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitude among the BEd students in respect of their caste categories i.e, Unreserved (M=46.45, SD= 4.8, N=497), Scheduled Caste (M=46.34, SD= 4.46, N=298), Scheduled Tribe (M=46.69, SD= 4.76, N=64), Other Backward Caste (M=45.87, SD= 4.77, N=253). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.16 One-way ANOVA test for attitude of BEd students_Caste category wise

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	45.68	3	15.225	.68	.56 [#]	.002	.196
Within Group	24677.284	1108	22.272				
Total	24722.960	1111					

(# Not Significant at .05 level)

The above table 4.16 shows that, the calculated F (3, 1108) is .68 and p is .56 ($p > .05$). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H_0 is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no significant difference among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, very small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.002) is found among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

H₀9: There is no significant difference among the recipients under the several scholarships in respect of their attitude towards the same.

Table 4.17 Group Statistics; attitude of BEd student_Scheme wise

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Scheme Wise	N	Mean	Std Deviation
	Not Aailed	174	44.16	4.70
	SVMCM	782	47.31	4.53
	OASIS	115	45.50	4.79
	AIKYAREE	39	44.72	3.76
	NSP	2	43.00	1.41
Total		1112	46.53	4.72

Fig. 4.3 Means Plot_attitude of students_name of scholarship

It is observed from the above (Table 4.17) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of several schemes availed for them i.e, Not Aailed (M=44.16, SD= 4.7, N= 174), SVMCM (M= 47.31, SD= 4.53, N=782), OASIS (M=45.50, SD= 4.79, N= 115), NSP (M=43, SD= 1.41, N=2). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.18 One-way ANOVA test for attitude of BEd students_Schoiarship scheme wise

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	1727.71	4	431.93	20.79	.001*	.070	1.00
Within Group	22995.25	1107	20.77				
Total	24722.960	1111					

(*Significant at .05 level)

The table 4.18 shows that, the calculated $F_{(4, 1107)}$ is 20.79 and p is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, F is significant, therefore H_0 is rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist significant difference among the name of scholarship of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, medium effect size (Eta Squared = 0.07) is found among the several scholarship schemes of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

Table 4.19 Post Hoc Analysis

(I) Name of Scholarship	(J) Name of Scholarship	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
Not Availed	SVMCM	3.15	.001*
	OASIS	1.33	.015*
	AIKYASREE	.56	.490
	NSP	1.16	.720
SVMCM	Not Availed	3.15	.001*
	OASIS	1.81	.001*
	AIKYASREE	2.59	.001*
	NSP	4.31	.182
OASIS	Not Availed	1.33	.015*
	SVMCM	1.81	.001*
	AIKYASREE	2.59	.357
	NSP	2.50	.443
AIKYASREE	Not Availed	.56	.490
	SVMCM	2.59	.001*
	OASIS	.78	.357
	NSP	1.72	.603
NSP	Not Availed	1.16	.720
	SVMCM	4.31	.182
	OASIS	2.50	.443
	AIKYASREE	1.72	.603

(*Significant at .05 level)

4.2.2 Objective 2: To study the attitude of BEd students, towards several scholarship schemes, those were non-recipients of any schemes in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of applicant, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category.

H₀10: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between non-recipient students of govt. and private colleges.

Table 4.20 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students_types of college

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Types of college				
	Govt.		119	44.37	4.77
	Private		55	43.71	4.57

From the Table 4.20 it is observed that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of Govt college ($M = 44.37$, $SD = 4.77$, $N = 119$) and private college ($M = 43.71$, $SD = 4.57$, $N = 55$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.21 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of non-recipient students in respect of types of college

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Types of college (Govt vs Private)		.010	.92	.861	172	.39 [#]

([#] Not significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.21) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is .010 and corresponding p value is .92 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of types of college. Here, for attitude the variability is same in types of college, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.21 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between govt and private college students, the calculated $t_{(172)}$ value is .861 and p value is .39 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is not rejected and it can be said that, the non recipient students of govt college are not significantly different from the private college students with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study also obtained weak effect size ($d = 0.14$) between the attitude of private and govt. college students through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀11: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between female and male non-recipient students.

Table 4.22 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students_ gender

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Gender	Female			
			Male	106	43.53
		68	45.15	4.42	

From the Table 4.22 it is observed that, there is difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of female ($M = 43.53$, $SD = 4.79$, $N = 106$) and private

college ($M = 45.15$, $SD = 4.42$, $N = 68$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.23 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of non-recipient students in respect of gender

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender (Female vs. Male)		.49	.49	2.24*	172	.03

(* significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.23) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is .49 and corresponding p value is .49 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of gender. Here, for attitude the variability is same in gender, thus equal variance can be assumed.

Table 4.23 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between female and male non-recipient students, the calculated $t_{(172)}$ value is 2.24 and p value is .03 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at .05 level. So, H_{011} is rejected and it can be said that, the non-recipient female students are significantly different from the non-recipient male students with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study obtained modest effect size ($d = 0.35$) between the attitude of female and male BEd students through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀₁₂: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between rural and urban non-recipient students.

Table 4.24 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students_locale

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Locale				
		Rural		67	44.19
	Urban		107	44.14	4.61

From the Table 4.24 it is observed that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of rural ($M = 44.19$, $SD = 4.88$, $N = 67$) and urban ($M = 44.14$, $SD = 4.61$, $N = 107$) non-recipient students. Whether this difference is

statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.25 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of non-recipient students in respect of locale

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Locale (Rural vs. Urban)	.6	.44	.07 [#]	172	.94	

([#]Not significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.25) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is .6 and corresponding p value is .44 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of locale. Here, for attitude the variability is same in locale, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.25 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between rural and urban non-recipient students, the calculated $t_{(172)}$ value is .07 and p value is .94 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is not rejected and it can be said that, the rural non-recipient students are significantly different from the urban non-recipient students with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Weak effect size ($d = 0.01$) obtained between the attitude of rural and urban students through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀13: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between non-recipient hosteller and day scholar students.

Table 4.26 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students nature of applicant

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Nature of Applicant	Hosteller	18	44.89	5.03
		Day Scholar	156	44.08	4.67

From the Table 4.26 it is observed that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of hosteller ($M = 44.89$, $SD = 5.03$, $N = 18$) and day scholar ($M = 44.08$, $SD = 4.67$, $N = 156$). Whether this difference is statistically

significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.27 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of non-recipient students in respect of nature of applicant

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Nature of Applicant (Hosteller vs Day Scholar)	.34	.56	.69	172	.49 [#]	

([#] Not significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.27) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is .34 and corresponding p value is .56 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of nature of applicant. Here, for attitude the variability is same in nature of applicant, thus equal variance can be assumed.

Table 4.27 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between hosteller and day scholar students, the calculated t ($_{172}$) value is .69 and p value is .49 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at .05 level. So, H_{013} is not rejected and it can be said that, the hosteller are not significantly different from the day scholar with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study also obtained modest effect size ($d = 0.27$) between the attitude of hosteller and day scholar students through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀₁₄: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between graduate and post graduate non-recipient students.

Table 4.28 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient student_educational qualification.

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Educational qualification	Graduate	36	43.19	4.08
		Post Graduate	138	44.41	4.83

From the Table 4.28 it is observed that, there is difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of non-recipient graduate ($M = 43.19$, $SD = 4.08$, $N = 36$) and non-recipient post graduate ($M = 44.41$, $SD = 4.83$, $N = 138$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.29 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of non-recipient students in respect of educational qualification

Attitude towards Scholarship Scheme	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Educational qualification (Graduate vs Post graduate)		1.19	.28	1.39	172	.17#

(# Not significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.29) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 1.19 and corresponding p value is .28 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of educational qualification. Here, for attitude the variability is same in qualification, thus equal variance can be assumed.

Table 4.29 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of Attitude between graduate and post graduate students, the calculated $t_{(172)}$ value is 1.39 and p value is .17 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is not rejected and it can be said that, the graduate students are not significantly different from the post graduate students with respect to their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study also obtained weak effect size ($d = 0.17$) between the attitude of graduate and post-graduate students through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀15: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the academic disciplines of non-recipient students.

Table 4.30 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students academic discipline

	Academic Discipline	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Language	54	44.72	4.77
	Science	77	44.48	4.49
	Social Science	41	42.76	4.84
	Engineering & Technology	2	45.50	6.36
Total		174	44.16	4.70

It is observed from the Table 4.30 that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their academic disciplines i.e, language (M= 44.72, SD= 4.77, N= 54), science (M= 44.48, SD= 4.49, N= 77), social science (M=

42.76, SD= 4.84, N= 41), engineering & technology (M= 45.5, SD= 6.36, N= 2). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table 4.31.

Fig. 4.4: Attitude of non-recipient students in respect of academic disciplines

Table 4.31 Oneway ANOVA test for attitude of non-recipient students academic discipline

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	109.38	3	36.46	1.67	.18 [#]	.03	.43
Within Group	3716.12	170	21.86				
Total	3825.50	173					

[#]Not Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.31 shows that, the calculated $F_{(3, 170)}$ is 1.67 and p is .18 ($p > .05$). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H_0 is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no difference among the academic disciplines of non-recipient students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.03) is found among the academic disciplines of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

H₀16: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among caste categories on non-recipient students.

Table 4.32 Group Statistics; attitude of non-recipient students_caste category

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Academic Discipline	N	Mean	Std Deviation
	Unreserved	127	44.27	4.64
	Scheduled Caste	29	43.51	4.45
	Scheduled Tribe	6	45.67	7.06
	OBC	12	43.83	5.10
Total		174	44.16	4.70

Fig. 4.5: Attitude of non-recipient students in respect of caste categories

It is observed from the above (Table 4. 32) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their caste category i.e, Unreserved (M=, SD= 4.64, N= 127), scheduled caste (M= 43.52, SD= 4.45, N= 29), scheduled tribe (M= 45.67, SD= 7.06, N= 6), OBC (M= 43.83, SD= 5.1, N= 12). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.33 Oneway ANOVA test for attitude of non-recipient students caste category

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	28.36	3	9.45	.42	.74 [#]	.007	.13
Within Group	3797.14	170	22.34				
Total	3825.50	173					

([#]Not Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.33 shows that, the calculated $F_{(3, 170)}$ is .42 and p is .74 ($p > .05$). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H_{016} is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no difference among the caste categories of non-recipient students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, very small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.007) is found among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

4.2.3 Objective 3: To study the attitude of BEd students, towards scholarship schemes, those were recipient under any scheme in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of applicant, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category, name of scholarship availed for them.

To fulfil the above objective, null hypotheses H_{017} to H_{024} were formulated and tested which are follows;

H_{017} : There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship recipients between govt and private college.

Table 4.34 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students _Types of college

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Types of College	Govt.	521	47.53	4.6
	Private	417	46.27	4.44	

The Table 4.34 shows that, there is a slight difference in the mean scores in attitude of scholarship recipients of Govt college ($M = 47.53$, $SD = 4.6$, $N = 521$) and private college ($M = 46.27$, $SD = 4.44$, $N = 417$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or

not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.35 Independent samples ‘t’ test of attitude of recipient students_ Types of college

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance			‘t’ test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Types of College (Govt. vs Private)		1.23	.27	4.24*	936	.001

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.35) shows that, in case of Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance the calculated F value is 1.23 and corresponding p value is .27 ($p > .05$), for the variations in respect of Qualification. Here, for attitude the variability in the two conditions (Govt & Private) is the same, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.35 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between Govt and Private college students the calculated $t_{(936)}$ value is 4.24 and p is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is significant at .05 level. So, H_{017} is rejected. It can be said that, the students of govt college are different from the private college with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study also obtained modest effect size ($d = 0.28$) between the attitude of hosteller and day scholar students through Cohen’s (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀₁₈: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between female and male recipients.

Table 4.36 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient student gender

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Gender	Female			
			Male	560	46.63
			378	47.47	4.87

From the Table 4.36 it is shows that, there is difference in the mean scores in attitude of female students ($M = 46.63$, $SD = 4.36$, $N = 560$) and male students ($M = 47.47$, $SD = 4.87$, $N = 378$). Whether this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.37 Independent Samples ‘t’ test; attitude of recipient student in respect of gender

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance			‘t’ test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances not assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender (Female vs. Male)		6.88	.01	2.71*	748.61	.007

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.37) shows that, in case of Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 6.88 and corresponding p value is .01 ($p < .05$) for the variation in respect of gender. Here, for attitude the variability in the two conditions (female & male) is not same, thus equal variances not assumed.

This Table 4.37 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between female and male students, the calculated $t_{(748.61)}$ value is 2.71 and p value is .01 ($p < .05$). Hence, ‘ t ’ is significant at .05 level. So, H_{018} is rejected and it can be said that, the female students are significantly different from the male students with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Researchers also obtained weak effect size ($d = 0.18$) between the attitude of female and male students through Cohen’s (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀₁₉: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between rural and urban recipients.

Table 4.38 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_locale

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Locale	Rural	636	47.13	4.38
		Urban	302	46.63	4.99

From above (Table 4.38) it is observed that, there is a difference in the mean scores in attitude of rural students ($M = 47.13$, $SD = 4.38$, $N = 636$) and urban students ($M = 46.63$, $SD = 4.99$, $N = 302$). Whether, this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented bellow;

Table 4.39 Independent Samples ‘t’ test; attitude of BEd student in respect of locale

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance			‘t’ test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances not assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Locale (Rural vs. Urban)		5.15	.02	1.50 [#]	528.71	.134

[#]Not Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.39) shows that, in case of Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 5.15 and corresponding p value is .02 ($p < .05$) for the variation in respect of gender. Here, for attitude the variability in the two conditions (rural & urban) is not same, thus equal variances not assumed.

This Table 4.39 also shows in case of comparing the attitude between rural and urban students, the calculated $t_{(528.71)}$ value is 1.50 and p value is .134 ($p > .05$). Hence, ‘ t ’ is not significant at .05 level. So, H_{019} is not rejected and it can be said that, the rural students are same with the urban students with respect to attitude. Therefore, there is need to verify the magnitude of this significant effect. Researcher also obtained weak effect size ($d = 0.11$) between the attitude of rural and urban students through Cohen’s (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀₂₀: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between hosteller and day scholar students.

Table 4.40 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_nature of applicant

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Nature of Applicant	Hosteller	187	48.20	4.30
		Day Scholar	751	46.66	4.61

From the Table 4.40 it is observed that, there is slight difference in the mean scores in attitude towards scholarship schemes of hosteller ($M = 48.20$, $SD = 4.30$, $N = 187$) and day scholar ($M = 46.66$, $SD = 4.61$, $N = 751$). Whether this difference is statistically

significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.41 Independent Sample 't'- test; attitude of BEd students in respect of Nature of applicant

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance			't' test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Nature of Applicant (Hosteller vs Day Scholar)		1.68	.20	4.12*	936	.001

(*Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.41) shows that, in case of Levene's Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 1.68 and corresponding p value is .20 ($p > .05$) for the variations in respect of nature of application. Here, for attitude the variability is same in nature of applicant, thus equal variance can be assumed.

This Table 4.41 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between hosteller and day scholar BEd students, the calculated $t_{(936)}$ value is 4.12 and p value is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at .05 level. So, H_0 is rejected and it can be said that, the hosteller are significantly different from the day scholar with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Study also obtained weak effect size ($d = 0.11$) between the attitude of hosteller and day scholar through Cohen's (1988) standard (Becker, 2000).

H₀21: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship between graduate and post-graduate recipients.

Table 4.42 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_educational qualification

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Variations		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Educational Qualification	Graduate		271	46.62
Post Graduate			667	47.11	4.67

From above (Table 4.42) it is observed that, there is a difference in the mean scores in attitude of graduate ($M = 46.62$, $SD = 4.37$, $N = 271$) and post-graduate ($M = 667$, $SD = 47.11$, $N = 667$). Whether, this difference is statistically significant or not, further independent samples t-test was done. The result is presented in the following table;

Table 4.43 Independent Samples ‘t’ test of attitude of BEd students in respect of educational qualification

Attitude of Recipients towards Scholarship schemes	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance			‘t’ test for Equality of Means		
	Equal variances not assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Educational Qualification (Graduate vs Post Graduate)		4.52	.03	1.53#	531.66	.13

(# Not Significant at .05 level)

The analysis (Table 4.43) shows that, in case of Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance the F value is 4.52 and corresponding p value is .03 ($p < .05$) for the variations in educational qualification. Here, for attitude the variability in the two conditions (graduate & post-graduate) is not same, thus equal variances not assumed.

This Table 4.43 also shows in case of comparing the mean score of attitude between graduate and post-graduate students, the calculated t (531.66) value is 1.53 and p value is .13 ($p > .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is not significant at .05 level. So, H_0 21 is not rejected and it can be said that, the graduates are same with the post-graduates with respect to attitude. Study also obtained modest effect size ($d = 0.11$) between the attitude of graduate and post-graduate students through Cohen’s (1988) measure.

H₀22: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the academic disciplines of BEd students, those who are recipient of scholarship.

Table 4.44 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_academic discipline

	Academic Discipline	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Language	343	47.00	4.38
	Science	213	47.36	5.01
	Social Science	376	46.74	4.54
	Engineering & Technology	6	45.83	3.82
Total		938	46.97	4.59

Fig. 4.6: Attitude of recipient students in respect of academic disciplines

It is observed from the above (Table 4.44) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their academic disciplines i.e, language (M= 47, SD= 4.38, N= 343), science (M= 47.36, SD= 5.01, N= 213), social science (M= 46.74, SD= 4.54, N= 376), engineering & technology (M= 45.83, SD= 3.82, N= 6). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.45 Oneway ANOVA test for attitude of BEd students_academic discipline wise

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	61.24	3	20.41	.97	.41#	.003	.27
Within Group	19677.93	934	21.07				
Total	19739.16	937					

(#Not Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.45 shows that, the calculated $F_{(3, 924)}$ is .97 and p is .41 ($p > .05$). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H_0 is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no difference among the academic disciplines of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, very small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.003) is found among the academic discipline of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

H₀23: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the caste categories of BEd students, those who are recipient of scholarship.

Table 4.46 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_caste categories

Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	Caste Category	N	Mean	Std Deviation
	Unreserved	370	47.20	4.68
	SC	269	46.64	4.37
	ST	58	46.79	4.54
	OBC	241	47.02	4.71
Total		938	46.97	4.59

Fig. 4.7: Attitude of recipient students in respect of caste categories

It is observed from the above (Table 4.46) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their caste categories i.e, Unreserved (M= 47.20, SD= 4.68, N= 370), scheduled caste (M= 46.64, SD= 4.37, N= 269), scheduled tribe (M= 46.79, SD= 4.54, N= 58), and OBC (M= 47.02 SD= 4.71, N= 241). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following table:

Table 4.47 One-way ANOVA test for attitude of BEd students_Recipients_Caste Category wise

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	51.98	3	17.33	.82 [#]	.48	.003	.23
Within Group	19687.19	934	21.08				
Total	19739.16	937					

([#]Not Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.47 shows that, the calculated $F(3, 934)$ is .82 and p is .48 ($p > .05$). Hence, F is not significant, therefore H_{023} is not rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist no difference among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, very small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.003) is found among the caste categories of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

H₀₂₄: There is no significant difference in attitude towards scholarship among the different recipient groups of BEd students.

Table 4.48 Group Statistics; Attitude of scholarship recipient students_Name of scholarship

	Name of Scholarship	N	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude towards Scholarship schemes	SVMCM	782	47.31	4.53
	OASIS	115	45.50	4.79
	AIKYASREE	39	44.72	3.76
	NSP	2	43.00	1.41
Total		938	46.97	4.59

Fig. 4.8: Attitude of recipient students in respect of name of scholarship

It is observed from the above (Table 4.48) that, there are differences in the mean scores of attitudes among the BEd students in respect of their schemes i.e, SVMCM ($M= 47.31$, $SD= 4.53$, $N= 782$), OASIS ($M= 45.50$, $SD= 4.79$, $N= 115$), AIKYASREE ($M= 44.72$,

SD= 3.76, N= 39), and NSP (M= 43 SD= 1.41, N= 2). Whether these differences are statistically significant or not, further analysis of variance was done. The result is presented in the following.

Table 4.49 One-way ANOVA test for attitude of Recipients students_ Name of Scheme

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta Squared	Observed Power
Between Group	569.41	3	189.80	9.25	.001*	.03	.10
Within Group	19169.76	934	20.52				
Total	19739.16	973					

(* Significant at 0.05 level)

The above table 4.49 shows that, the calculated $F_{(3, 934)}$ is 9.25 and p is .001 ($p < .05$). Hence, F is significant, therefore H_0 is rejected. So it can be interpreted that, there exist difference among the scholarship schemes of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. Here, small effect size (Eta Squared = 0.03) is found among the different schemes of scholarship of BEd students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship programme.

Table 4.50 Post Hoc Analysis

(I) Name of Scholarship	(J) Name of Scholarship	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
Not Aailed	SVMCM	3.15	.001*
	OASIS	1.33	.015*
	AIKYASREE	.56	.490
	NSP	1.16	.720
SVMCM	Not Aailed	3.15	.001*
	OASIS	1.81	.001*
	AIKYASREE	2.59	.001*
	NSP	4.31	.182
OASIS	Not Aailed	1.33	.015*
	SVMCM	1.81	.001*
	AIKYASREE	2.59	.357
	NSP	2.50	.443
AIKYASREE	Not Aailed	.56	.490
	SVMCM	2.59	.001*
	OASIS	.78	.357
	NSP	1.72	.603
NSP	Not Aailed	1.16	.720
	SVMCM	4.31	.182
	OASIS	2.50	.443
	AIKYASREE	1.72	.603

(*Significant at 0.05 level)

Follow-up analyses is necessary due to the presence of significant difference among the groups of scholarship to recognize where the significant difference lie. Analysis in the Table 4.50, contains multiple comparisons across the groups of scholarships with the help of most liberal, Fisher's LSD post hoc test. Analysis shows that, non recipients' students were differed from the students of SVMCM and OASIS schemes. This suggested students under SVMCM scheme were differed from OASIS, AIKYASREE scheme and also differed from students were not availed any scholarship programme. Students under OASIS programme were differed from the students under SVMCM and AIKYASREE schemes. On the other hand, students under AIKYASREE schemes were differed from the students of SVMCM schemes.

Fate of Hypotheses (H_01 to H_024)

Present researchers use the following table (4.51) to show the fate of hypotheses according to the objectives that analysed through independent samples t-test and ANOVA;

Table 4.51 Fate of Hypotheses with respect to Independent Sample t- test & ANOVA

Null Hypotheses	Variables		Decisions	Effect Size
	Dependent	Independent (Category Wise)		
H_01	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Govt & Private college	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Modest ($d = 0.11$)
H_02	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Female & Male	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Modest ($d = 0.21$)
H_03	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Rural & Urban	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Weak ($d = 0.18$)
H_04	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Hosteller & Day Scholar	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Modest ($d = 0.37$)
H_05	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Under-Graduate & Post-Graduate	Not Rejected ($p = .17$)	Weak ($d = 0.09$)

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H₀₆	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Eligible & Not Eligible	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Moderate ($d = 0.56$)
H₀₇	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Language, Science, Social Science, Engineering & Technology	Not Rejected ($p = .71$)	Very Small ($\eta^2 = .001$)
H₀₈	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	Unreserved, SC, ST, OBC	Not Rejected ($p = .56$)	Very Small ($\eta^2 = .002$)
H₀₉	Attitude of BEd students towards scholarship scheme	SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE, NSP	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Small ($\eta^2 = .07$)
H₀₁₀	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Govt & Private college	Not Rejected ($p = .39$)	Weak ($d = .14$)
H₀₁₁	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Female & Male	Rejected ($p = .03$)	Modest ($d = .35$)
H₀₁₂	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Rural & Urban	Not Rejected ($p = .94$)	Weak ($d = .01$)
H₀₁₃	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Hosteller & Day Scholar	Not Rejected ($p = .17$)	Modest ($d = .27$)
H₀₁₄	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Under-Graduate & Post-Graduate	Not Rejected ($p = .49$)	Weak ($d = .17$)
H₀₁₅	Attitude of Non-recipient students towards scholarship	Language, Science, Social Science, Engineering & Technology	Not Rejected ($p = .18$)	Small ($\eta^2 = .03$)

Chapter- IV / Analysis & Interpretation

	scheme			
H₀16	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Unreserved, SC, ST, OBC	Not Rejected ($p = .74$)	Very Small ($\eta^2 = .007$)
H₀17	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Govt & Private college	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Modest ($d = .28$)
H₀18	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Female & Male	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Weak ($d = .18$)
H₀19	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Rural & Urban	Not Rejected ($p = .12$)	Weak ($d = .11$)
H₀20	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Hosteller & Day Scholar	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Weak ($d = .11$)
H₀21	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Under-Graduate & Post-Graduate	Not Rejected ($p = .14$)	Modest ($d = .35$)
H₀22	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Language, Science, Social Science, Engineering & Technology	Not Rejected ($p = .41$)	Very Small ($\eta^2 = .003$)
H₀23	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	Unreserved, SC, ST, OBC	Not Rejected ($p = .48$)	Very Small ($\eta^2 = .003$)
H₀24	Attitude of Recipient students towards scholarship scheme	SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE, NSP	Rejected ($p = .00$)	Small ($\eta^2 = .03$)

4. B Descriptive Statistics Used

4.2.4 Objective 4: To measure the awareness of the trainees on several issues concerning with scholarship schemes available for them.

To analyse the whole awareness into several specific issue, these are too much pertinent with the schemes of scholarship concerned. Those issues were i.e.,

Table 4.52 Scheme wise distribution

Sl. No.	Scholarship	Recipients	Percentage
1	SVMCM	782	83.37
2	OASIS	115	12.26
3	AIKYASREE	39	4.16
4	NSP	2	0.21
Total		938	100

Table 4.52 shows that, out of total recipients (N=938) of scholarship schemes 83%, 12.26%, 4.16% and only .21% are belongs to SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE and NSP respectively. Table also express that, most of the BEd students are getting scholarship from the concerned dept. of State Government (WB). Very insignificant number of trainees is benefitted from the scholarship of concerned department, Government of India.

Fig. 4.9: Scheme wise distribution of beneficiaries in colleges

To fulfil the objective 4, researchers has framed the following research question, which is following;

RQ.1: What are the statuses of awareness about scholarship schemes in BEd students from the perspective of following issues?

1. Scholarship schemes and the Govt. department concerned.
2. Amount of scholarship available for them.
3. Family income limit.
4. Obtained score (%) in last examination.
5. Reliable source of information in scholarship.
6. Person entrusted within institution.
7. Steps to be followed in pending situation.
8. Willing to expense the scholarship amount.
9. Whom to be intimated after getting scholarship.

4.3.4.1 Scholarship schemes and the Govt. department concerned:

Table 4.53 Awareness on scholarship running by the specific gov. Department

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	760	81
2	Not Aware	178	19
Total		938	100

Table 4.53 shows that, in case of awareness about the name of particular gov. department by which scholarships are sanctioned and disbursed, 81 % students are well-known about the name of Govt. department and 19 % are unknown about the name of that specific Govt. department by whom scholarships are sanctioned and allotted.

Fig. 4.10: Proportion of recipients about the name of Govt. Dept.

4.3.4.2 Amount of scholarship available for them.

Table 4.54 Awareness on scholarship amount (Rs)

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	729	77.7
2	Not Aware	209	22.3
Total		938	100

Table 4.54 shows awareness of students about the amount of scholarship (Rs.) they will receive finally. Out of total recipients (N = 938) 77.7 % students are aware and 22.3 % are not aware about how much money will be available for them under such scheme of scholarship.

Fig. 4.11: Proportion of recipients about the Amount of scholarship (Rs.)

4.3.4.3 Family income limit:

Table 4.55 Awareness on Annual family income of the recipient students

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	335	35.7
2	Not Aware	603	64.3
Total		938	100

Table 4.55 shows, in case of awareness about the annual family income (Rupees) limit, which is a significant criterion in the process of getting scholarship. Unfortunately study shows, out of total recipients (N=938), 35.7 % are aware and rest of 64.3 % are not aware on that particular issue.

Fig. 4.12: Proportion of recipients about the Annual family income (Rs.)

4.3.4.4 Obtained score (%) in last examination:

Table 4.56 Awareness on Eligibility of Merit

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	640	68.2
2	Not Aware	298	31.8
Total		938	100

Table 4.56 shows that, in case of consciousness about the minimum score obtained in last examination (in %), which is also an important criterion in the process of getting scholarship, out of total recipients (N=938) 68.2 % are mindful and rest of 31.8 % are unmindful on that specific issue.

Fig. 4.13: Proportion of recipients about eligibility of merit

4.3.4.5 Reliable source of information in scholarship:

Table 4.57 Awareness on most reliable sources of information

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	623	66.4
2	Not Aware	315	33.6
Total		938	100

Table 4.57 shows that, in case of consciousness about the most reliable source of information regarding scholarship programme (eligibility, application, verification, sanction, allotment etc criterions), based on every steps of the applicants are guided by. Sadly out of total recipients (N=938) 66.4 % are careful and rest of 33.6 % are careless about the same.

Fig. 4.14: Proportion of recipients about the most reliable source of information

4.3.4.6 Person entrusted within institution:

Table 4.58 Awareness on person entrusted for scholarship matter within institution

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	29	3.1
2	Not Aware	909	96.9
Total		938	100

Study (Table 4.58) found that, in case of awareness about the person entrusted for scholarship matter at institute level, Sorrowfully out of total recipients (N=938) only 3.1 % are alert and rest of 96.9 % are casual about that entrusted person.

Fig. 4.15: Proportion of recipients about the entrusted person within institution

4.3.4.7 Steps to be followed in pending situation:

Table 4.59 Awareness on steps to be followed during pending situation

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	443	47.2
2	Not Aware	495	52.8
Total		938	100

Table 4.59 shows that, in case of consciousness about the steps to be followed in pending or delaying at district/state level regarding scholarship programme, miserably out of total recipients (N=938) 47.2 % are concerned and rest of 52.8 % are unconcerned about what to do on that time to move out from the issue.

Fig. 4.16: Proportion of recipients about the steps to followed in pending situation

4.3.4.8 Willing to expense the scholarship amount:

Table 4.60 Awareness on willing to expense the scholarship amount

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	802	85.5
2	Not Aware	136	14.5
Total		938	100

Study (Table 4.60) shows that, in case of awareness of students about the preference to expense the amount of scholarship programme, out of total recipients (N=938) 85.5 % are aware and rest of 14.5 % are not aware about to on which purpose the amount should be expense.

Fig. 4.17: Proportion of recipients willing to expense the scholarship amount

4.3.4.9 Whom to be intimated after getting scholarship:

Table 4.61 Awareness on Person to be intimated after getting the scholarship

Sl. No.	Status	Recipients	Percentage
1	Aware	71	7.6
2	Not Aware	867	92.4
Total		938	100

Study (Table 4.61) shows that, in case of awareness about the person to be intimated after getting scholarship, out of total recipients (N=938) only 7.6 % are concerned and 92.4 % are careless about the same issue.

Fig. 4.18: Proportion of recipients Person to be intimated after getting the amount

4.2.5 Objective 5: To measure the awareness of BEd trainees on such criteria concerning with scholarship schemes.

To fulfill the above mentioned objective following research question is formulated;

RQ.2: How many of the BEd students are aware about the general issues of scholarship schemes in W.B.?

To answer the above mentioned research question percentage analysis is done with following awareness issues;

1. Preference on most reliable sources of information.
2. Awareness on Application Submission & Verification.
3. Awareness about whom to contact in pending Situation.

4. Awareness on Willing to Expense.
5. Awareness on whom to be intimidated.

4.2.5.1 Preference on most reliable sources of information:

Table 4.62 Preference on most reliable sources of information

Sl. No.	Option	Recipients	Percentage
i.	News Paper	26	2.8
ii.	Peer Group	86	9.2
iii.	Institute Nodal Officer	200	21.3
iv.	District Office	3	0.3
v.	Official Website	623	66.4
Total		938	100

Study revealed that, regarding the students' awareness about from which sources (Table 4.62) they are benefitted to know the criteria of eligibility, application, verification and sanction procedure, as a reliable source official website of scholarship portal, Nodal officer at institute level, peer friends, news papers and district office are poses 66.4%, 21.3%, 9.2%, 2.8%, 0.3% percentages respectively.

Fig. 4.19: Preference on most reliable sources of information

4.2.5.2 Awareness on Application Submission & Verification:

Table 4.63 Liability of Application Submission & Verification

Sl. No.	Option	Recipients	Percentage
i.	Head of Institute	465	49.6
ii.	Institutional Nodal Officer	44	4.7
iii.	District Nodal Officer	7	0.7
iv.	State Nodal Officer	14	1.5
v.	I don't know	408	43.5
Total		938	100

Study found that, regarding the students' awareness about (Table 63) the technical name of liable person / officer at their institute level by whom application submission and verification process is made. Out of total (N = 938), 49.6% are agreed with HoI, 4.7% are with INO, 1.5% SNO, and 0.7% believes DNO. Surprisingly, 43.5% students goes with the option that, they have no idea about the person/officer concerned all about within the institute.

Fig. 4.20: Liability of Application Submission & Verification

4.2.5.3 Awareness about whom to contact in pending Situation:

Table 4.64 Awareness about whom to contact in pending Situation

Sl. No.	Option	Recipients	Percentage
i.	Principal	43	4.6
ii.	College Office	213	22.7
iii.	District Office	112	11.9
iv.	Toll-free Number	445	47.4
v.	I don't know	125	13.3
Total		938	100

Regarding the students' awareness about whom or where need to contact if the verification is pending either district level of state level. Out of total (N = 938), 47.4% are wants call on toll-free help line, 22.7% are goes to college office, 11.9% are moves to district office and only 4% students likes to meet their principal to come out from the situation. Unfortunately, 13.3% students go with the option that, they don't know about whom to visit in this context.

Fig. 4.21: Awareness about whom to contact in pending Situation

5.2.5.4 Awareness on Willing to Expense:

Table 4.65 Awareness on Willing to Expense

Sl. No.	Option	Recipients	Percentage
i.	Family Purpose	64	6.8
ii.	Pay fees at college	815	86.9
iii.	Social service	13	1.4
iv.	Personal Hobbies	14	1.5
v.	None of the above	32	3.4
Total		938	100

Regarding the willingness of students to expenses the amount of scholarship, analysis shows that, out of total (N = 938) students, 86.9% are ready to pay the tuition fees of college. Rest of 6.8%, 1.5% and 1.4% are willing to expenses in family purposes, personal hobbies, social services respectively. But 3.4% of Students are not willing to expenses the scholarship amount to the said areas.

Fig. 4.22: Awareness on Willing to Expense

5.2.5.5 Awareness on whom to be intimated.

Table 4.66 Awareness on whom to be intimated

Sl. No.	Option	Recipients	Percentage
i.	Parents	550	58.64
ii.	Friends	14	27.93
iii.	Institute Nodal Officer	76	3.84
iv.	Everyone of above	262	8.10
v.	None of above	36	1.49
Total		938	100

Regarding the awareness about whom to intimated after getting the scholarship amount, study found that, out of total (N = 938) most of the students (58.64%) are intimates their parents, friends are intimated by 27.93% students, and only 3.8% students are intimates their Institute Nodal Officer/person. But, 8.1% students goes with everybody mentioned earlier are intimated. But, 1.49% students declare no one will be intimated after getting the scholarship amount from the concerned Govt. department.

Fig. 4.23: Awareness on whom to be intimated

4. C Thematic Analysis

4.2.6 Objective 6: To understand the nature of workload of the Nodal Officers, apart from their academic activities.

To fulfill the above objective following research question framed by the investigators;

RQ.3: What kind of workload considered by the nodal officers at college level?

To answer the research question 3 the transcribed data analysed thematically and some codes were emerged. After the consideration of the similarity in codes, those are clubbed into a category.

Code 1.	Dissatisfaction	}	Task Burden (Category -1)
Code 2.	Annoyance		
Code 3.	Troubleness		
Code 4.	Lack of Academic Enjoyment		

Interpretation of data with respect *Task Burden*: As per the opinion of the nodal person, scholarship activity continues from the beginning to the end of the academic year and it is like a regular assignment. In that sense a full-time employee is required to manage this matter, but the colleges are severely understaffed. Nodal officer of several colleges are reported that, there are different scholarship opportunities for the students of BEd in W.B. Each scheme have separate online portal and each of one has to submit different documents according the rules mentioned there, which is quite burden for them. Nodal officers are dissatisfied totally, due to absence of guideline or departmental order to make it successful with satisfaction.

Nodal officer stated that, scholarship work is a tremendous amount of hassle full. The question and answer session with the students continued throughout the week even out of college hour. They feel annoyed to answer same questions through phone call, whatsapp. They have replied that, they have to do those things under a kind of compulsion. Some time college authority also pressurise for supplying the data regarding scholarship instantly. They thought that, many of the students apparently do not need financial aid, but they are eager also to come under the scheme. Nodal persons annoyed to submit hard copy of application forms (OASIS) after online verifying in concerned portal.

Nodal officer mentioned that, without prior discussion with the staff, authority suggested their name as nodal officer to the concerned scholarship portal. As a teacher they thought that, the students are worried more about scholarship than about teaching learning activity. This is a matter of regret for them that, the income certificates that students submitted along with application form are no doubt valid but hard to believe. The entire portals always are not functioning properly. As a result officers feel bore due to the requirement of more time. They feel trouble during the login in portals.

Teachers were come into this profession thinking that, they would be primarily involved in academic activities, but they could not accept the work related to scholarship as an additional responsibility. They believe that, the work they do on scholarship is purely clerical job. Sometimes students become interested in discussion of scholarship during content discussion in the classroom. It is very regrettable for nodal officer that, students never call them to know anything about study. But students are always calling them and ask various questions about the scholarship.

Reflective Notes: However, the nodal person expressed that, being involved in scholarship activities new experiences they had gained and enriched them professionally. But investigator noticed an anomaly in his / her facial expression during the comments given that, they don't take the duties related to scholarship as a professional pressure. They felt happy as a part of institutional contribution when students get financial support. Some of them commented that, their main duty is to help their students.

4.2.7 Objective 7: To know the condition of awareness of the Nodal Officers about the procedure of several scholarship schemes.

To fulfill the above objective following research question framed by the investigators;

RQ.4: What is the condition of awareness of Nodal Officers at college level regarding verification and forwarding to next level?

To answer the research question 4, the transcribed data analysed thematically and some codes were emerged. After the consideration of the similarity in codes, those are clubbed into a category.

Code-5.	No training / orientation organised	}	Apathy in Training and Documents (Category -2)
Code 6.	Online meeting conducted		
Code 7.	Guidebook or user manual		

Interpretation of data with respect *Apathy in Training and Documents*: Nodal person concerning with scholarship activity opined that, they had never received training or orientation by the specific department of government regarding the same. Even either at district or block level nothing was ever organised for nodal persons at institute level. They noticed that, almost every year some new features were added to the scholarship portal, unfortunately they have no information or guideline on that issue.

In October, 2022 an online meeting conducted by the department of higher education about Swami Vivekananda Merit Cum Means Scholarship for the college principals and nodal persons. On that session basically resource person explained the technical aspects of the portal step by step and nodal persons listened. There was no question answer session on that day, so that would not be called orientation in that sense. Although, several scholarships are available for BEd students, no training has been conducted till now for nodal officers.

As per the opinion by the nodal officers, there is no guidebook or user manual available for the verification process and other allied matter of scholarship programme. They are forced to inquire from the nodal persons of other colleges known to them if there is any hurdle in the verification process. In some cases nodal officers got the solution of the problem from the district level or block level officials over phone call. Officers mentioned that, there are toll-free numbers in each portal. Number is only used to registered problem, no solution or instant answer are available from that corner of helpline. One kind of nodal person is there who use his long experience and no guidebook or manual is required for those people.

Reflective Notes: Although, both the scholarship of state or central government is same in respect of providing training/ orientation and guidebook / user manual to the institute nodal officer. Comments made by the nodal person that, they embarrassed and frustrated after facing the situation, when they get information from the students regarding scholarship. Nodal officer opposed, to disclose their personal details like, aadhaar number, phone number, email, etc., because, they are the representatives of college. Personal identity should create complexity in future.

4.2.8. Objective 8: To study the perception of Nodal Officer regarding genuine interest of recipients of different scholarship schemes.

To fulfill the above objective following research questions (RQ.5 & RQ. 6) framed by the investigators;

RQ.5: What is the opinion of the nodal officer regarding the interest of students between scholarship and academic matter?

To answer the research question 5, the transcribed data analysed thematically and some codes were emerged. After the consideration of the similarity in codes, those are clubbed into a category.

Code 8.	Neutral about academic and scholarship matter	}	Conflict in Academic Involvement and Scholarship Programme (Category -3)
Code 9.	Much interested on scholarship than academic activity		

Interpretation of data with respect *Conflict in Academic Involvement and Scholarship Programme*: A number of nodal officer possessed neutral view regarding the conflict between academic and scholarship matter of the students. Such nodal person argued that, students are more interested on which area, is much difficult to realise for them. As per the comments made by the nodal officer that, this issue is a matter of research whether, students are more inclined towards scholarship or not.

Nodal officers are agreed that, most of the students are more interested in scholarship than their academic matter during BEd course. Even in the discussion within classroom, nodal officers faced trouble. There have a serious issue raised by the nodal officer that, students of BEd tend to claim multiple scholarship in one academic session, depending on students' previous experience in undergraduate and post-graduate level.

Reflective Note: Most of nodal persons / officers were trying to answer correct technically, when asked about the issues of miss using scholarship or using scholarship inappropriately by their students. Some of them were straightly replied without any

hesitation that, as per their concern such number of students getting the benefits of scholarship inappropriately. But, they have no scope to resist those applicants.

RQ.6: What is the opinion of nodal person regarding the misuse of scholarship among the students?

To answer the research question 6, the transcribed data analysed thematically and some codes were emerged. After the consideration of the similarity in codes, those are clubbed into a category.

Interpretation of data with respect *Use and Misuse of Scholarship*: Nodal person found that, the amount of scholarship money is not sufficient to pursue the BEd programme, as a result use it properly by the students. In the process of verification income certificate plays a vital role. If that certificate issued from concerned authority, then there is no chance of misuse. As per the statement given by students nodal teacher replied that, a number of students use the amount as expenditure towards family purposes. Few nodal person avoid the issue regarding misuse of scholarship by the students that, an inquiry would be need to take the real picture of scholarship.

According to the comments of nodal officer that, they don't know all the students personally, that's why no comments on the matter of misuse of scholarship. But officers mentioned that, such number of students applies in the scheme as a hosteller, rather they are not. Because scholarship amount for hosteller is higher than the day scholar. Even some cases also found by the nodal person of the college, after enrolment of the course students apply in online portal and verification also done by them. But those students are dropout without completing the BEd course. Nodal persons also experienced that, such number of students applies in online portal using their institution name. Actually, those students have no connection with that college. However, to get the scholarship that technique has adopted by the unknown students. Teacher in Charge of Dr. B. R.

Ambedkar College, Betai, nadia complained that, ninety nine outside people were submit fake application in their institutional portal. Students also apply for scholarship, though their parents are in government job. Nodal person understand that students are misusing the scholarship but as a nodal officer he/she cannot do anything as per the rules.

Reflective Notes: Issuance of income certificate from gram panchayat / counselor and e-certificate from the concerned portal is too much easy in our society. Sometimes they seem that, it will be better if it is not mandatory. Officers also mentioned that, the benefits of state government scholarship in BEd course are not available to those students, who completed their last degree in other states, out of West Bengal.

Figure 4.24: Flow chart of thematic analysis

On the basis of the meaningfulness of the categories a general or core theme was developed;

Realisation of nodal officer on scholarship

Description of theme with respect to categories: Among all kind of support service available at school, college and university level in field of academic programme, getting scholarship is the most important to the students recently. These entire scholarship programmes are not the liability of government department, but the concerned institutions also. This study is particularly focused on the scholarship as a part of student support service in teacher education institute. At institute level a person is additionally charged about the verification and forwarding process of application form through the specific online portal. Due to the different kinds of rules and regulations of each scholarship nodal persons are feels it as a burden in their profession. There is no specific guideline or order from the concerned department to conduct such kind of activity, their assignment regarding scholarship schemes are running surprisingly. However, Principal of the colleges is careless about this matter. As a nodal person of scholarship matter, some time they seem that, certain percent of students are misusing this scholarship practically. But technically, they cannot do anything. Students are more interested and active in the matter of scholarship. Whereas, the academic interest of the students is decreasing day by day. This part of support service is important because huge amount of financial liabilities are there. Unfortunately, all activities are completed through taken as granted method in teacher education institutes of W.B.

CHAPTER - V

FINDINGS, DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with the summary of the research, findings, discussion, conclusion and recommendations for further studies.

5.2 Summary of Research Work

5.2.1 Objectives of the Study:

- 1) To study the attitude of BEd students towards scholarship schemes available in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, types of students, educational qualification, eligibility, academic discipline, caste category, types of scholarship availed for them.
- 2) To study the attitude of BEd students, towards several scholarship schemes, those are non-recipients any schemes in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category.
- 3) To study the attitude of BEd students, towards scholarship schemes, those are recipients under any scheme in W.B. in relation to their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, academic discipline, caste category, types of scholarship availed for them.
- 4) To measure the awareness of the trainees on several issues of scholarship schemes available for them.
- 5) To measure the awareness of the trainees on such criteria concerning with scholarship schemes as a part of student support service.
- 6) To study the role of the institute about the process of verification concerning with several scholarships available for students.
- 7) To study the attitude of the Institutional Nodal Officer towards the several scholarship schemes as a part of student support services.

5.2.2 Research Design: In this project investigators used multi-method design of research. Present researcher attempted to study the attitude and awareness of BEd students regarding several schemes of scholarship available for them in West Bengal. Thus, keeping objectives of this study, descriptive survey method was used in this part.

Similarly, present researchers also attempted to realise the attitude and awareness of Nodal officers / Persons, who engaged at institute level regarding the process of application form submission, verification, & forwarding of scholarship schemes to respective portal. Thus keeping objectives of this part qualitative analysis also made.

5.2.3 Population: Prospective teachers, who are pursuing their Bachelor of Education (BEd) programme in West Bengal and the all those Nodal Teacher or Officer or Person, who are liable to their institute as well as to their students in terms of all the activities associated with scholarship schemes and as a part of students support service.

5.2.4 Sample: In this study, eight districts from the southern part of West Bengal were considered at the starting of sample frame. Sixteen teachers training institutes were identified randomly to fix the sample unit. From those unites researchers considered BEd students (N=1112) randomly. Simultaneously, fourteen Nodal officers were taken from those teachers training institute concerned.

5.2.5 Variables: In this study two major variables are studied; (i) Attitude and (ii) Awareness of stakeholders about scholarship. The study was conducted with nine different contextual situations, which are following;

1. Types of B.Ed. college (Govt. & Private),
2. Gender of students (Male & Female),
3. Location of college (Rural & Urban),
4. Nature of applicant (Hosteller & Day Scholar),
5. Educational Qualification (Graduate & Post-graduate),
6. Eligibility (Eligible & not eligible),
7. Academic discipline (Language, Science, Social science, & Engineering-technology)
8. Caste category (Unreserved, Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe, & Other Backward Caste)
9. Name of scholarship (SVMCM, OASIS, AIKYASREE, NSP, & Non Recipients)

5.2.6 Tools Used in the Study

5.2.6.1 Questionnaire to measure Attitude of Students: To measure the attitude of students towards scholarship schemes a self made Likert type questionnaire (Appendix-I) has standardised by the researchers.

5.2.6.2 Questionnaire to measure Awareness of Students: To measure the awareness of students about several scholarship schemes researchers develop a multiple choice answer type questionnaire (Appendix-II).

5.2.6.3 Semi Structured Interview Schedule: To realise the attitude and awareness of nodal officer/ nodal teacher at institute level, researchers develop a semi-structured open ended interview schedule (Appendix- III).

5.2.7 Statistical Techniques Employed: Analysis of the study is conducted with the following statistical techniques;

5.2.7.1 t-test: As the objectives of the present study demand to compare attitude of BEd students in respect of their types of college, gender, locale, nature of application, educational qualification, eligibility, academic discipline, caste categories, name of schemes variations. For this purpose t-test has been employed to find out the significant difference.

5.2.7.2 ANOVA: As the objectives of the present study demand to compare attitude of B.Ed. students in respect of their academic discipline, caste categories, name of schemes variations. For this purpose ANOVA has been employed to find out the significant difference.

5.2.7.3 Effect Sizes: Here, present researchers interpreted each analysis with respect to their null hypothesis. Where interpretations not only considered by mentioning statistical significance existed or not, effect sizes of each analysis also done i.e., Cohen's *d*, and Partial Eta Squared for t test, and ANOVA respectively.

5.2.7.4 Percentage Analysis: In this report such research questions were answered through the Percentage analysis. It is appropriate to know how many of the participants gave a particular answer. This means that the responses fall in different categories, such as aware or not-aware, different caste group, and scholarship scheme etc.

5.2.8 Thematic Analysis: By the use of this technique researchers found the perception of nodal person towards scholarship programme in teachers training institute in WB. To realise the workload, awareness, attitude of the nodal person total institute level.

5.3 Findings of the Study

The findings of the study are given bellow (with corresponding **Objective/ Hypothesis**).

1. Students of govt BEd college are different from the students of private BEd college in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O1/H₀1)**
2. Female students are not same with the male students in respect of their Attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O1/H₀2)**
3. Rural students are different from the urban students in terms of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O1/H₀3)**
4. Hostellers are not same with the day scholars with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O1/H₀4)**
5. Graduate students are same with post graduate student in respect of attitude towards scholarship programme. **(O1/H₀5)**
6. Attitude towards scholarship schemes is different in respect of students' eligibility of application. **(O1/H₀6)**
7. Attitude towards scholarship schemes of the BEd students are same among the disciplines academic groups. **(O1/H₀7)**
8. Attitude towards scholarship schemes of the BEd students are same among the caste categories. **(O1/H₀8)**
9. But, students under different scholarship schemes are different from each others in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O1/H₀9)**
10. Non recipient BEd students of govt. college are same with the private college with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O2/H₀10)**
11. Non-recipient female students are different from the non-recipient male students with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O2/H₀11)**
12. Non-recipient students are same with the urban non-recipient students with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O2/H₀12)**
13. Non-recipient hostellers are same with the day scholar with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O2/H₀13)**

14. Non-recipient graduate students are equal with the post graduate students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O2/H₀14)**
15. No difference in attitude among the students of different academic disciplines of non-recipient BEd students. **(O2/H₀15)**
16. Non-recipient students are same in their attitude among the caste categories of **(O2/H₀16)**
17. Recipient students of govt. college are different from the private college with respect to their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O3/H₀17)**
18. Recipient female students are not same with male students in respect of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O3/H₀18)**
19. Recipient rural students are same with the urban students in terms their attitude. **(O3/H₀19)**
20. Recipient hostellers are not same with day scholars in terms of their attitude towards scholarship schemes. **(O3/H₀20)**
21. Recipient graduates are same with the post-graduates in respect of their attitude. **(O3/H₀21)**
22. Attitude towards scholarship schemes is same among the academic disciplines of recipients BEd students. **(O3/H₀22)**
23. Attitude towards scholarship schemes is same among the caste categories of recipients BEd students. **(O3/H₀23)**
24. Attitude towards scholarship schemes is not same among the students of recipients under different schemes. **(O3/H₀24)**
25. **Awareness regarding several issues (O4/RQ1):** Study revealed that, out of total participants in this study, 83.37 percent students in BEd colleges are benefited through SVMCM scholarship, 12.26 percent are under OASIS portal, 4.16 percent students are under the AIKYASREE portal and only 0.21 percent goes with NS Portal. Students of BEd in WB are getting financial support from the several schemes of scholarship running by different department of Government of WB. **(i)** Most of the students (81%) are aware about the name of concerned department, from which the funding is disbursed to the students. **(ii)** How much money is allotted in a particular scholarship scheme is known by 77.7 percent students. **(iii)** Information regarding the family income is not a serious

matter to the students of BEd college, as a result 64.3 percent trainees are not aware about the income bar in application process. (iv) Most of scholarship scheme have a specific merit criterion for students. But unfortunately, 31.8 percent of students are not conscious about the issue. (v) 33.6 percent students of BEd colleges are not aware about the reliable sources of information regarding scholarship programmes. (vi) A huge number of students (96.9%) are ignoring the activity of nodal person/ officer at their institute level concerning to scholarship activity. Actually, students have no idea about such kind of person and liabilities concerned to him/ her, to support their scholarship programme. (vii) Students of BEd (52.8%) are not aware about the steps to be followed during the pending situation of scholarship process. (viii) It is a good sign to found that, 85.5 percent students of BEd colleges are aware about the area; where to expense the scholarship amount they have received. (ix) After getting the scholarship amount, 92.4 percent students are not willing to intimate anybody about the matter of scholarship.

26. Awareness regarding preference of several criterions (O5/RQ2): (i) Present researchers in this study tried to know which areas students most value for their scholarship work. 66.4 percent students depend on specific official website of scholarship for most reliable information, 21.3 percent of students rely on college, 9.2 percent depend on their peer group, 2.8 percent rely on news paper and 0.3 percent depends on the district office regarding the scholarship matter. (ii) Study found that, 49.6 percent students feel that, the responsibility of the scholarship related activities rests with the head of the institution, 4.7 percent students feel that, institutional nodal officer should be approached for these tasks. Similarly, 1.5 percent and 0.7 percent students consider approaching state nodal officer and district nodal officers for scholarship related assignments. From the study it was found that, 43.5 percent students are not sure who they should approach for the same reason. (iii) As a result of the study, 47.4 percent students take toll-free number for help, 22.7 percent students contact to the college office, 11.9 percent student contact the district office and 4.4 percent students contact with the college principal, when they face trouble in scholarship related issue. Unfortunately, 13.3 percent students are don't know what should the need to do during pending situation of scholarship matter. (iv) It is found that multiple areas prioritised by the students to spend their scholarship money. These priority areas of the students comprising with family

purpose (6.8%), paying college fees (86.9%), social service (1.4%), personal hobbies (1.5%) and none of these (3.4%). (v) The study asked students who they think should be intimated after receiving scholarship money? 58.6 percent students think parents should be informed, 27.93 percent students think friends should be intimated, 3.84 percent BEd students think institutional nodal person/ officer should be informed by them. But, 8.1 percent students think every one of the mentioned earlier should be intimated and 1.49 percent student thinks no one should be informed after getting the scholarship amount.

27. Workload of the Nodal Person (O6/RQ3): Findings concerning to the work load of the nodal person / officer apart from scholarship activities are emerged from the interview with them. Study found that, the assignments regarding scholarship activity is a task burden to them, which is divided into four areas, i.e. (i) Dissatisfaction upon the activities they have done as a nodal officer of a particular scholarship scheme. (ii) They feel annoyance to do the work on regular basis; similarly both the side beneficiaries and concerned govt. departments are non cooperative about the system running properly. (iii) Nodal officers / persons are feel trouble to deal the matter in terms of their mental satisfaction. (iv) Finally, all the work related to scholarship is purely clerical in nature. There is no academic enjoyment replied by the person entrusted at college level.

28. Awareness of the Nodal persons (O7/RQ4): In order to know the awareness of nodal officers regarding scholarship schemes, principal investigator participated in the interview process with them. Study found that, there is apathy in training and documents about the scholarship schemes in our state, faced by the nodal officers since a long duration as per their experience. No training programme or no orientation session has been organized by the concerned departments of the scholarship schemes at either district or state level in WB. Online meeting conducted in 2022 for one hour duration, but that is not sufficient to understand the whole process of scheme. There is no such guidebook or order has been supplied for nodal person at institute level. As a result they are not confirmed about, their activity either right or wrong on a regular basis.

29. Perception of Nodal Person about the Miss Use of scholarship (O8/RQ5 & RQ6): To realise the perception of nodal teacher regarding the interest of students on scholarship programme investigators conducted interview with nodal person. Study revealed that, there is a strong conflict between academic and financial interest of the

students on their regular behaviour within the college premises. Such percent of students are much interested on scholarship than academic matter. A little amount of students also are there who are balanced on both the aspects of their college life. Some of the nodal officer replied that, the chances of misuse of scholarship is very limited in WB, on the other hand, some of them are agreed upon the issue of scholarship used by the students improperly in BEd colleges.

5.4 Discussion

It is observed from the findings that, in case of attitude of overall BEd (both, recipients & non-recipients) students' educational qualification, academic disciplines and caste categories are not involved directly with scholarship schemes. But, attitude of the students change in the variations of types of college, gender, and locale, nature of application, eligibility, and scholarship availed for them. In case of non-recipient BEd students findings revealed that, attitude is same with the variation of college type, locale, nature of applicants, educational qualification, academic discipline and caste categories. On the other hand non-recipient students' attitude towards scholarship scheme is influenced by their gender only. Whereas, recipients students attitude towards scholarship programme is influenced by their college type, gender, nature of application, different schemes also. But attitude is same in respect of their locale, educational qualification, and academic discipline and caste variations.

Awareness of the recipient students of BEd colleges showed a surprising picture of scholarship related issues. Each of the scholarship either state govt. or central govt are given by a particular department in every year. Eighty one percent beneficiaries are aware about the name of particular department and nineteen percent are unaware about the same. There are such differences in the scholarship amount in respect of different criterion. All the scholarship schemes announced the specific amount have to be disbursed after fulfilling the conditions by students. Study found that, around seventy seven percent students are aware about the scholarship amount (Rs), and rest of the students are casual in this matter. Every scholarship has its own criterion about means (family income) in annual basis. Without fulfilling this criterion there is no possibility to apply in such scholarship scheme. Though, around thirty six percent students are aware about this criterion, and sixty four percent students are totally unmindful on income limit

of family. Scholarship schemes are also given on specific merit requirement. Here, merit indicates the percentage of obtained score by the student in his last examination passed out. Therefore it also plays an important role in eligibility criterion to apply in scholarship programme. Surprisingly near about sixty eight percent are aware and rest of students are unaware about it. All these students who are eligible to get scholarship in BEd course they need to inform about the proper guideline and procedure to follow as their necessity. Study shows that, sixty six percent students are aware about the most reliable sources of information for them regarding scholarship. Thirty four percent students are not aware about it. Facilities of scholarship are impossible without the support of educational institution. In every scholarship there is an entrusted person assigned by the concerned institute as an additional duty/ charge. Institutional support ensured by the nodal officer/ nodal teacher / nodal person. But, study revealed that, only three percent students are aware about that particular person entrusted by the college. There are separate online portal for every scholarship programme, where we can find the details regarding whole scheme, eligibility criterion, submission process, etc. Even contact number and email address also available for help to the students. Here, a point also needs to mention that, in each steps of verification process every student will be intimated through text message in their registered mobile number. However, due to official delay or may be due to the technical error in portal, process of forwarding is lengthy. So, delaying in the process or pending situation in the scholarship process is very common phenomena in students experiences. Around forty seven percent students are aware to resolve this pending situation, and around fifty three percent are unaware about the condition. The objective of scholarship is to giving financial support to the students for their education. In this regard eighty six percent students are conscious about to expense the amount, but around fifteen percent are undecided to expense the scholarship amount. As a part of student support service, every institute have the right to inform how many of students are getting benefitted from different scholarship schemes. Similarly, students have a liability to intimate the person entrusted within college after getting the benefits from scheme. But surprisingly, around eight person students are aware about to intimate the nodal person in their colleges.

This study also reveals such significant awareness issues, which are very much interesting to our student support activity. First of all most of the students (66.4 %) are dependent on official website of the concerned portal. This is a healthy picture of their awareness regarding sources of information they have believed. But if we consider the other sources Nodal officer in college (21.3%), peer group (9.2%), news paper (2.8%) and District office (0.3%) the proportion is not well. Students (49.6%) are agreed about the matter of application verification and forwarding process is completed through the head of institution. Whereas, students rely on institute nodal officer (4.7%), district nodal officer (0.7%), and state nodal officer (1.5%) for the verification process. Surprisingly, 43.5% students confirmed that, they have no idea about whose liability is to verify and forward the application. Too much casualness is the only reason behind it.

After verify and forward the online application by the institute students are intimated on their mobile number, registered with the portal. Sometime the forwarding process is delayed due to technical or official ground. On that situation most of the students (47.4%) prefer to call at toll free number available at portal. To know the reason of delay 11.9% students prefer to visit district office. Visit to college office made by 22.7% students. And 4.6% students are directly meet with the college principal to mention the issue of delay. But, there are also a number of students (13.3%), who have no idea about what to do during that situation. That means this percent of students are not exactly expecting the scholarship as a financial support.

All of us are very well known that, scholarship is the financial support to the students to continue their education. In this context researchers are trying to find out the awareness of willing to expense the scholarship amount. Very large number of students (86.9%) are agreed to pay the tuition fees of college. Similarly students mentioned several purposes like family (6.8%), social service (1.4%), and personal hobbies (1.5%) also included. But, 3.4% students are replied that, they have expense the amount rather than the area mentioned before.

When we consider the benefits of scholarship through institutional linkage, that means such kind of support is essential here. As a normal perception of the beneficiaries there should be a reply from the student is very much expected. Researchers think that, it is too

much rational from the perspective of student support. Unfortunately, this liability has not established among the recipient students. Only, 3.84% students are intimate to the institute nodal officer. Fortunately, parents (58.64%), and friends (27.93%) are intimated by the students. Apart from these students (8.1%) are intimate to all i.e. parents, friends, and nodal officer. But, a small number of students are there, who are not willing to intimate any one about their benefits.

Apart from regular activity of the college most of the nodal person feels that the assignment of scholarship scheme is a task burden to them. Most probably, their regular institutional activity could be hampered. Academic focus could be shifted from regular to scholarship matter. Personal life supposed to suffer after taking the charge of nodal person. Without training and guide manual of the whole process of dealing is not too easy among them. They are incapable to help properly to their students regarding several issues of scholarship. They are motivated towards scholarship as an additional duty and a part of student support. Nodal Persons are not confident in the process of online verification and forwarding of application form of students. Students were too anxious about the matter of money in the form of scholarship. Without, proper guidance at institute they also feel unhappy to complete the process of scholarship disbursement. Surprisingly, students feel that, the regular attendance should not be considered as a criterion of eligibility to scholarship scheme. College authority is reluctant to ensure the daily attendance of their students in academic purpose. Students are strongly willing to get the benefits of more than one scholarship in an academic session. Guidelines to fill up the application are in English language, which is difficult to understand by the trainees to submit their application in online portal. Maximum students are depending to submit their application form on cyber cafe. Such kind of mistakes or errors also made by the guys assists to fill up the form. Some time instruction for students within portal and events happened in practical situation is not correlated by the students during the verification and submission process, that's why students feels disappointed what to do and how to do analyse the fact. As a helping hand for scholarship students are always preferred to contact with toll free number provided in respective portal. In any situation students are not interested to communicate with their college principal concerned. Payment of college tuition fees is the most priority of students. On the other side a

significant percentage of students willing to expense the amount of scholarship to fulfil their personal hobbies and social service.

5.5 Educational Implication

It is anticipated that, the result of this study will assist teachers training institute as a part of student support service by creating new avenues for the development of positive attitude and awareness of stakeholders about the scholarship schemes. On the other hand policy maker and several govt. officials and administrators will feel about what they have to do to support in the name of scholarship.

5.6 Conclusions

Present study concludes that, attitudinal perspective of BEd students in WB is different in respect of several factors considered here. In some cases the attitude of the BEd trainees are same towards the scholarship schemes available for them. In terms of awareness study concluded that, students are aware in several criterion. However, enough awareness is not found here. On the other hand nodal persons are not taking this additional duty spontaneously. They are facing trouble and annoyed to deal the matter of scholarship on regular basis. Several factors are involved within their experiences. Perception of nodal persons towards student regarding scholarship programme is also not good. To make more success in this system too many modification and changes are required. Govt department should be adopting such new policy for nodal persons as well as students to support financially according to the genuineness of the students background.

5.7 Limitations of the Study

This study is an attempt to investigate the attitude of BEd students towards scholarship programmes available in West Bengal. Here the researcher presents some issues that might be investigated usefully in future studies of attitudes and awareness of stakeholders and allied matters for more perceptive.

- (1) To take a broad view the conditions of scholarship at college level in stakeholders, more districts of West Bengal should be included.
- (2) Sample size should be enlarged for much consistent result in the field of scholarship programme.

- (3) For the development of attitude measuring tool more criteria and items can be added.
- (4) In the process of tool development of awareness regarding scholarships, scheme specific criterion should be incorporated.
- (5) In case of realising, the attitude of nodal teacher, data should be recorded through video graphs in face to face mode.

5.8 Suggestions for further Study

- (1) Study on scholarship in BEd college can be conducted among other colleges (i.e. Primary teaches training college, general degree college, nursing college, polytechnic college, Pharmacy College, engineering college, medical college, university level, and school level also)
- (2) This study took position in a specific circumstance and over a limited time. It would reveal to carry out similar studies on the basis of a longer phase of time in some different regional contexts. Such study is able to provide a deeper and comfortable understanding of attitude and awareness of stakeholders.
- (3) Research on scholarship could be conducted on a broad area to increase reliability of interpretation; even additional factors should be taken for consideration.

These are the examples relating to scholarship programme, attitude and awareness of stakeholders which is describe for possible investigation in the future. Hope, this study might serve as a foundation for further studies within this common field of student support service in the BEd college of West Bengal.

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